

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Report on implementation of the methodological framework for user-centred quality on selected services

DELIVERABLE 6.2

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Abstract

This D6.2 report presents the results of a structured usability evaluation of the GoTriple multilingual research discovery platform, conducted within UCQ-FRAME, a user-centred quality framework for assessing the usability of scholarly communication services. As a core service within OPERAS, GoTriple plays a key role in facilitating multilingual discovery for SSH research. The evaluation aimed to validate and refine UCQ-FRAME, while identifying strengths and usability challenges in order to improve the usability, efficiency and long-term sustainability of GoTriple.

A triangulated UX evaluation approach was used, combining heuristic evaluation (HE), moderated usability testing (MUT) and unmoderated remote usability testing (URUT) to provide a comprehensive usability evaluation. The results highlighted both strengths and usability issues: HE evaluators described GoTriple's UI as visually appealing, clean and well structured, while MUT participants appreciated its modern look and intuitive navigation. However, usability challenges were also identified, including navigation inconsistencies, difficulty in understanding the platform's mission and target audience, unclear search filtering, and gaps in bibliographic metadata.

The evaluation findings were prioritised according to severity, providing a structured roadmap for incremental usability improvements. The results also validated UCQ-FRAME as a multi-method UX evaluation framework, reinforcing its role in future OPERAS service evaluations.

Next steps include completing the URUT evaluation, implementing prioritised usability improvements, conducting follow-up testing, and further refining UCQ-FRAME to ensure a sustainable, user-driven approach to usability evaluation.

Table of Contents

Document Log.....	3
Abstract.....	4
Abbreviations.....	8
Executive summary.....	10
List of figures.....	13
List of tables.....	13
1 Introduction.....	15
1.1 Aims of OPERAS-PLUS and WP6.....	15
1.2 User-centred design and UCQ-FRAME.....	15
1.3 Purpose of the evaluation.....	16
1.4 Scope of the report.....	16
1.5 Structure of the report.....	17
1.6 Intended audience.....	17
2 Related work.....	18
3 Implementation focused research questions and objectives.....	19
4 Evaluation methodology.....	20
4.1 Overview of the evaluation approach.....	20
4.2 Evaluation methods.....	21
4.2.1 Heuristic evaluation (HE).....	21
4.2.1.1 Scoring criteria: Nielsen's 10 usability heuristics.....	21
4.2.1.2 Evaluation process.....	22
4.2.1.3 Severity criteria and expert consensus.....	23
4.2.2 Moderated usability testing (MUT).....	24
4.2.2.1 Participant selection and profile.....	25
4.2.2.2 Lab testing setup.....	26
4.2.2.3 Remote testing setup.....	27
4.2.2.4 Testing process & key tasks.....	28
4.2.2.5 Usability metrics and data collection.....	29
4.2.3 Unmoderated usability test (URUT).....	31
4.2.3.1 Participant selection & sample size.....	31
4.2.3.2 Test procedure & key tasks.....	31
4.2.3.3 Usability metrics and data collection.....	32
4.2.3.4 URUT execution & technical considerations.....	34

4.3	Ethical considerations.....	36
5	<i>Findings & recommendations.....</i>	37
5.1	Overview of usability problems identified.....	37
5.1.1	High severity usability problems (Critical/Major).....	37
5.1.1.1	Search functionality & filtering issues.....	37
5.1.1.2	Navigation & homepage structure.....	39
5.1.1.3	Language switching & multilingual support.....	41
5.1.1.4	Bibliographic records & citation functions.....	41
5.1.1.5	Account registration & authentication issues.....	43
5.1.2	Structured and actionable recommendations.....	44
5.2	Strengths and positive aspects of GoTriple.....	47
5.2.1	User interface and visual design.....	47
5.2.2	Search functionality and features.....	47
5.2.3	Content organisation and accessibility.....	49
5.2.4	User account management and system reliability.....	50
5.2.5	Navigation and information architecture.....	50
6	<i>Insights for UCQ-FRAME.....</i>	51
6.1	Strengthening UCQ-FRAME's multi-method evaluation strategy.....	52
6.2	Adapting heuristics for research platforms.....	53
6.3	Improve usability problem prioritisation and tracking.....	53
6.4	Exploring the feasibility of sustainable participant recruitment and research panels.....	54
6.5	Overcoming technological barriers and test setup efficiency in URUT studies.....	55
6.6	Preparation and pilot testing of usability studies: Managing cognitive load and fatigue.....	56
6.7	Lack of a centralised repository for user research insights.....	58
6.8	Post-fix usability validation: Ensuring the real impact of implemented changes.....	59
6.9	Improving UCQ-FRAME for sustainable usability and UX evaluation.....	60
7	<i>Conclusion and next steps.....</i>	61
7.1	Evaluating key findings through the research questions.....	61
7.1.1	Key usability problems affecting GoTriple.....	61
7.1.2	Effectiveness of GoTriple in supporting common tasks.....	62
7.1.3	Comparison of evaluation methods: HE, MUT and URUT.....	62

7.1.4	Refine GoTriple and UCQ-FRAME based on the results (RQ4).....	63
7.2	Next steps and areas for further research.....	64
7.2.1	Improving mobile and responsive usability.....	64
7.2.2	Evaluation of advanced features (Knowledge Map, Streamgraph, AI Chatbot).....	65
7.2.3	Assessing long-term user engagement and content relevance.....	65
7.2.4	Continuous benchmarking and iterative UX improvements.....	66
References.....		67
Appendices.....		68
Appendix A - Heuristic review checklist.....		68
Appendix B - MUT script in English and consent form in Croatian.....		80
Appendix C - URUT script in English with consent form.....		94
Appendix D - Extracts from HE, MUT, and URUT reports.....		115
Appendix E - Methodological guidelines for HE, MUT, and URUT.....		119
	How to conduct a HE for scholarly communication and open science services.....	119
	How to conduct a MUT for scholarly communication and open science services.....	123
	How to conduct URUT for scholarly communication and open science services.....	127

Abbreviations

AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (legal status under Belgian law for international non-profit associations)
AoC	OPERAS Assembly of Commons
EA	OPERAS Executive Assembly
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HCD	Human-Centred Design
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
ISO 9241	Multi-part standard from the International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network EC-funded project
MUT	Moderated Usability Test
NPS	Net Promoter Score
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OS	Open Science
PD	Participatory Design
PWDR	People Who Do Research
ResearchOps	Research Operations (community)
RI	Research Infrastructure
RQ	Research Question
SAC	OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG	OPERAS Special Interest Groups
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STB	OPERAS Services and Technology Board

SUS	System Usability Scale
UCD	User-Centred Design
UCQ-FRAME	OPERAS-PLUS D6.1: Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives
UEQ-S	User Experience Questionnaire - Short version
UI	User Interface
URUT	Unmoderated Remote Usability Test
UX	User Experience
TBD	To Be Determined
WP	Work Package
WP6	Work Package 6 of the OPERAS PLUS project

Executive summary

This OPERAS-PLUS D6.2 report presents the results of a structured usability evaluation of the multilingual research discovery platform **GoTriple**, conducted within the framework of **UCQ-FRAME**, a user-centred quality framework for assessing the usability of scholarly communication services (OPERAS-PLUS D6.1). As a core service within OPERAS, GoTriple plays a crucial role in facilitating multilingual discovery for social sciences and humanities (SSH) research. The **LUMEN** project is expected to further enhance the platform and broaden its disciplinary scope. Ensuring its usability, efficiency and long-term sustainability is crucial to fostering adoption and engagement.

The evaluation aimed to refine UCQ-FRAME while assessing GoTriple's usability, identifying strengths and areas for improvement to better align the platform with researchers' needs.

To achieve these goals, a **triangulated UX evaluation approach** was used to ensure a comprehensive assessment of usability challenges from multiple perspectives:

- **Heuristic Evaluation (HE):** Experts evaluated GoTriple using Jakob Nielsen's (1994) usability heuristics to identify system-level usability challenges.
- **Moderated Usability Testing (MUT):** Real users performed research tasks while being observed, uncovering workflow challenges, navigation difficulties and user behaviour patterns.
- **Unmoderated Remote Usability Testing (URUT):** Ongoing, collecting System Usability Scale (SUS) and User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ-S) scores to measure perceived usability, efficiency and satisfaction at scale.

Findings were synthesised from HE, MUT, and URUT reports, which remain temporarily confidential pending further processing. This report provides key insights to guide usability improvements and UCQ-FRAME refinements.

Key findings and insights

The usability evaluation of GoTriple revealed a well-structured and visually coherent platform, but certain usability issues affected user workflows. While the platform provides a clean interface, clear search workflows, and multilingual research support, users encountered navigation difficulties, metadata inconsistencies, and filtering inefficiencies that impacted efficiency and task completion.

The evaluation identified both platform strengths and usability challenges, providing a comprehensive perspective on the GoTriple user experience.

Positive aspects identified

- **Interface and navigation:** The clean, minimalist design provided a positive first impression and supported intuitive navigation. Three out of five HE evaluators specifically praised the structured layout, and MUT participants noted that the interface was visually appealing and in line with UX expectations for research

discovery platforms.

- **Search functionality:** The search system was simple and effective, with good visibility of system status, clear input fields and an intuitive query process. Users appreciated the ability to copy queries, which allowed them to refine searches more efficiently. Language filtering was identified as a particularly valuable feature, supporting multilingual research workflows.
- **Content organisation and discoverability:** Features such as TRIPLE Vocabulary tags, keyword linking and structured metadata presentation were well received for improving content discovery. Participants appreciated the "Related Projects" feature, which helped users explore additional relevant resources.
- **Account management and system reliability:** The registration and authentication process demonstrated robust error prevention, with four out of five HE evaluators confirming its reliability. The registration process was noted for its recognition rather than recall approach, which reduced the cognitive load for new users.

Usability problems identified

Despite these strengths, several usability problems were identified::

- **Navigation issues:** Unclear home page labels (e.g. "Membership" and "Data Services") and a lack of help or documentation caused confusion and made it difficult for users to understand the platform's key features.
- **Searching and filtering:** While the search system was highly intuitive, the filtering logic was unclear and participants noted a lack of visible feedback when applying filters. Inconsistent categorisation of results contributed to confusion and led some users to believe that filters did not work as expected.
- **Bibliographic metadata and citation/reference management:** Users struggled to find full-text access links and critical metadata such as DOIs, author affiliations and reference export options. This led to inefficiencies in research workflows as participants had to manually extract missing information.
- **Account management and login experience:** Although technically stable, the registration process lacked clear form validation, error messages and login confirmation feedback. New users were often unsure if their authentication was successful.
- **Multilingual usability and translation consistency:** Translation inconsistencies and terminology variations between languages created additional cognitive load for non-English speakers. Some users mistakenly believed that changing the UI language also changed the language of search results, leading to frustration and lower task completion rates.

To address the usability issues identified, a prioritised set of recommendations has been defined to ensure that the most critical issues are addressed first, while allowing for ongoing refinement.

Despite these usability problems, GoTriple remains a solid foundation for scholarly discovery, particularly through structured content linking and multilingual support.

Implications for development and UCQ-FRAME

To facilitate effective collaboration with the development team, the findings were structured into a prioritised usability roadmap, ensuring that incremental usability improvements could be implemented while balancing feasibility and impact. The severity-driven approach ensured that the most pressing usability problems were addressed first, while allowing for iterative refinement to improve the overall user experience.

Beyond **the usability evaluation of GoTriple**, this evaluation validated **the effectiveness of UCQ-FRAME** as a multi-method usability evaluation framework. The combination of HE, MUT and URUT demonstrated that triangulated UX evaluations are essential for capturing system-level and user-driven usability insights. These findings will support future OPERAS service evaluations by ensuring that usability testing is systematic, iterative and integrated into platform development rather than conducted as a one-off assessment.

Conclusion and next steps

By incorporating these findings into the iterative development of GoTriple, the platform can enhance usability, engagement, and efficiency, ensuring its continued relevance in SSH research. In addition, the findings from this evaluation will contribute to the ongoing refinement of UCQ-FRAME, ensuring that it remains a robust methodology for user-centred quality assessment in SSH research infrastructures.

Next steps include:

- Completing the URUT evaluation to validate usability perceptions at scale.
- Implementing prioritised usability improvements and refinements, particularly in the areas of search optimisation, metadata completeness, and multilingual consistency.
- Conduct follow-up evaluation and testing to assess the impact of improvements.
- Continue to refine UCQ-FRAME, incorporating lessons learned into future OPERAS service evaluations.
- Include accessibility considerations in future usability studies to ensure that GoTriple remains inclusive of diverse communities.

This report highlights the importance of ongoing usability evaluation to ensure that GoTriple remains a user-friendly and effective research discovery tool.

List of figures

Figure 1: Expert 1 HE checklist - documenting usability violations	23
Figure 2. Participant 1 in local lab setup - OBS recording and streaming	27
Figure 3. MUT - Participant 3 in remote session (Google Meet) - Identifiable image used with explicit consent of participant	28
Figure 4: Screenshot of all MUT recordings - documentation of usability test sessions conducted in laboratory and remote environments	30
Figure 5. URUT Task 2 - Searching for publications: Clickstream navigation and task success rate	33
Figure 6. Loop 11 modes of response - screen, audio and text based participation in URUT	35
Figure 7. Recommendation: Implement advanced search options	38
Figure 8. Recommendation: Implement the ability to exclude or include more than one filter at a time.	39
Figure 9. Recommendation: explain why "Tailored for you" is recommended	40
Figure 10. Recommendation: Explain what "Membership" and "Data Services" mean	40
Figure 11. Recommendation: Improve translation (in this example, Croatian language)	41
Figure 12. Recommendation: Expand export options beyond BibTeX and JSON to include APA, Harvard, MLA, Chicago, and IEEE, improving integration with reference managers like Zotero	42
Figure 13. Recommendation: Extend bibliographic record data, e.g. publication title, pages, DOI, type of licence, affiliation, type of document, etc.	43
Figure 14. Recommendation: Add the green button "Full text option" button to the main results list and to the right of the full bibliographic record screen	43
Figure 15. Recommendation: Provide a clear process for password requirements and validation	44
Figure 16. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: the possibility to copy search queries	48
Figure 17. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: graphical visualisation of the publication date filter	48
Figure 18. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: visualisations	49
Figure 19. One of the positive features are the coloured tags in the bibliographic record: disciplines, keywords, TRIPLE Vocabulary tags	49
Figure 20. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: related projects and authors	50

List of tables

Table 1. Severity rating scale for usability problems based on Nielsen's 0–3 scale (Nielsen, 1994).	23
Table 2. Overview of usability testing tasks, scenarios, and objectives in the GoTriple evaluation	28
Table 3. Overview of usability testing tasks, scenarios, and objectives.	32

Table 4. Usability improvement roadmap: prioritised recommendations and implementation effort 45

1 Introduction

1.1 Aims of OPERAS-PLUS and WP6

OPERAS is a European research infrastructure dedicated to supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It provides a collaborative framework for researchers, publishers and institutions to promote multilingual discovery services, open access publishing and digital research tools. OPERAS is also recognised as an ESFRI project, reinforcing its role in promoting Open Science across Europe (OPERAS-EU, 2024).

The OPERAS-PLUS project (2022-2025) has been initiated to further develop and sustain the OPERAS infrastructure, ensuring that its services evolve to meet the diverse needs of SSH researchers and stakeholders. Within this initiative, WP6 focuses on user engagement and training, and aims to integrate UCD/HCD methodologies into OPERAS services (OPERAS-EU, 2024).

A key objective of WP6 is to ensure that OPERAS services are developed based on real user needs, improving usability, accessibility and engagement. Deliverable D6.2 contributes to this objective by **evaluating the usability and user experience of GoTriple, identifying usability problems and recommending improvements based on user research and best practices in user-centred design (UCD)**. By applying structured usability methods, this deliverable supports the OPERAS vision of promoting open science through intuitive and accessible digital research infrastructures.

1.2 User-centred design and UCQ-FRAME

UCD is a widely recognised best practice for developing intuitive, accessible and effective digital systems. According to ISO 9241-210:2010, UCD ensures that systems are usable and useful by focusing on user needs, applying human factors and usability research, and conducting iterative design and evaluation (NIST, 2024).

Within OPERAS-PLUS, UCQ-FRAME has been developed in WP6 as a methodological framework to ensure user-centred quality assessment in OPERAS services (Pehar, Juric, & Peša Pavlović, 2024). UCQ-FRAME provides a structured and iterative UCD process that enables platforms such as GoTriple to systematically evaluate and improve usability, accessibility and user satisfaction.

UCQ-FRAME emphasises:

- **Understanding user needs through research** - Conducting usability studies to identify barriers and opportunities for improvement.
- **Iterative design and evaluation** - Implementing continuous improvements based on user feedback.
- **Improving UX maturity** - Ensuring that OPERAS services are aligned with best practices in usability, accessibility and engagement.

By integrating UCQ-FRAME into the GoTriple evaluation, D6.2 will ensure that the

evaluation follows global best practices in usability and human-centred design. The results of this evaluation will not only contribute to the improvement of GoTriple, but will also support the wider **application of UCQ-FRAME in other OPERAS services**, thus strengthening a structured approach to user-centred quality assessment in open science platforms.

1.3 Purpose of the evaluation

The primary purpose of the evaluation was to identify usability problems on the GoTriple¹ platform.

The success of GoTriple depends not only on the volume of aggregated research data, but also on its **usability** - the extent to which users can effectively and efficiently achieve their research goals while having a satisfactory experience. Usability, as defined by ISO 9241-11 (1998), is the degree to which specified users can achieve their intended goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a particular context of use.

This integrated evaluation was conducted to assess whether GoTriple meets these user-centred quality standards, ensuring that researchers, students and librarians can navigate the platform seamlessly, refine their searches with ease and access relevant research results without frustration.

Specifically, **the evaluation sought to:**

- **Identify usability problems** related to navigation, search filtering and multilingual functionality.
- **Assess overall usability perception and efficiency**, incorporating the SUS and UEQ-S metrics.
- **Provide actionable recommendations** to improve the design and functionality of the platform to enhance accessibility, user engagement and research discoverability.

1.4 Scope of the report

This report (D6.2) summarises the results of a **triangulated UX evaluation**, including:

- **HE** (expert review of UI/UX principles to identify usability violations).
- **MUT** (task-based observations with real users, gathering qualitative feedback).
- **URUT** (ongoing quantitative evaluation to further validate and examine the usability issues, assess the importance of selected design recommendations and assess the overall user experience with UEQ and SUS).

These evaluations focused on **key user interactions**, including:

- **Home page and navigation** - Assessing first impressions, menu clarity and

¹ Go Triple. <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

overall user orientation.

- **Search and filtering** - Assessing search efficiency, filtering logic and feedback mechanisms.
- **Bibliographic records** - Assessing clarity of metadata, accessibility of full text and availability of citations.
- **Account management (login/registration)** - Examine registration processes, clarity of authentication and feedback mechanisms.
- **Multilingual interface** - Identifying translation inconsistencies, usability barriers for non-English users, and language switching challenges.

1.5 Structure of the report

The report is organised as follows

- **Methodology** - Describes how the evaluations were conducted, including heuristic principles, participant demographics, test scenarios, and usability metrics.
- **Summary of Findings** - Provides a comprehensive overview of the usability findings, detailing the number and severity of issues identified for each method.
- **Detailed Findings & Recommendations** - Breaks down specific usability problems by category (navigation, search, filtering, bibliographic records, account management, multilingual interface) and outlines targeted UX/UI recommendations.
- **Insights for UCQ-FRAME** - Discusses how the findings contribute to the refinement of the User-Centric Quality Framework (UCQ-FRAME), ensuring its effectiveness for future evaluations of OPERAS services.
- **Conclusion and next steps** - Summarises key findings, answers research questions, analyses how results from heuristic evaluation, moderated usability testing and unmoderated usability testing compare, and presents a roadmap for implementing usability improvements, including future research directions such as mobile usability, advanced GoTriple features, longitudinal user engagement, and benchmarking iterations.

1.6 Intended audience

This report is intended for

- The GoTriple Committee, Strategic Groups (SGs) and Advisory Board, comprising key stakeholders responsible for overseeing and implementing usability improvements to ensure the platform evolves in response to user needs.
- OPERAS members and other stakeholders interested in applying UCQ-FRAME to other scholarly communication services and monitoring the impact of GoTriple to ensure its alignment with open science goals.

By focusing on the usability problems and their solutions, this report provides a clear, actionable roadmap for improving the user experience of GoTriple and ensuring its long-term success as a sustainable, user-friendly discovery platform.

2 Related work

This evaluation is founded on established UX principles and methods. A foundational first applied method is Nielsen's **Heuristic Evaluation**, a usability technique introduced by Nielsen & Molich (1990), in which expert reviewers assess interfaces based on usability heuristics. This cost-effective approach identifies usability problems without the need for extensive user testing. Further, **usability testing** with users (moderated and unmoderated) were conducted.

Moreover, ISO 9241-210 (2019) provides UCD/HCD guidelines to ensure iterative user engagement in interface development (Pehar & Peša Pavlović, 2023), emphasising usability, accessibility, and satisfaction.

The UCQ-FRAME methodology builds on these **frameworks** by integrating multiple evaluation methods, research operations, and human-centred design principles:

- Nielsen's (1994) Heuristics - Usability principles applied to interface evaluation.
- Peter Morville's (2004) UX Honeycomb - Expands UX evaluation beyond usability to include findability, credibility and desirability.
- Double Diamond 2.0² - Extends design processes with principles, method banks and a culture of innovation.
- ResearchOps (2019) - Standardised research management, governance and scalability.
- ISO 9241-210 (2019) - Aligns UX evaluation with human-centred design principles.

This structured yet adaptable approach allows for a coherent evaluation of the OPERAS services, including GoTriple.

GoTriple competes with platforms such as Google Scholar, OpenAIRE and SSH databases, each with different UX strengths and challenges (Dumouchel et al., 2020):

- Google Scholar³ - Simple search, but lacks SSH-specific filtering and multilingual support.
- OpenAIRE⁴ - Aggregates open access content, but faces metadata challenges that limit search capabilities.
- GoTriple - Aims to fill these gaps with multilingual and interdisciplinary discovery tools, but faces challenges in search refinement, metadata structuring and navigation.

Previous research from the TRIPLE project highlights the fragmentation of research

² Double Diamond 2.0. <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/the-double-diamond/>

³ Google Scholar. <https://scholar.google.com/>

⁴ OpenAIRE. <https://www.openaire.eu/>

resources as a major UX barrier (Dumouchel et al., 2020). SSH research is scattered across repositories, languages and formats, making integration of resources a challenge. This evaluation assesses whether GoTriple successfully addresses these barriers through search and browsing functionalities, as well as multilingual support.

Open science platforms need to balance functionality with usability and serve a diverse audience - from researchers to policy makers. Research by Dumouchel et al (2020) has shown that **successful platforms require platforms require:**

- **Clear guidance for new users** - Many are unfamiliar with open access repositories.
- **Intuitive multilingual interfaces** - To avoid bias and ensure consistency of translation.
- **Building trust through UX** - Encouraging researchers to use specialised platforms rather than general search engines.
- **Incorporate co-design methods** - Involve end-users in shaping platform features.

This study evaluates whether GoTriple effectively supports a user-friendly, multilingual and discoverable SSH research ecosystem. Using Nielsen's heuristics, ISO 9241, UCQ-FRAME and ResearchOps, it provides a robust framework for UX evaluation.

3 Implementation focused research questions and objectives

The evaluation was guided by a number of key research questions and objectives, formulated in line with the UCQ-FRAME methodology and the objectives of WP6:

- **RQ1: What are the key usability problems affecting the GoTriple platform?**
 - o **Objective:** Identify and categorise usability problems by severity to understand which aspects of the interface are most problematic for users (e.g. navigation, search, content comprehension). This addresses the UCQ-FRAME goal of diagnosing quality gaps in the user experience.
- **RQ2: How effective does GoTriple support users in performing common tasks (e.g. finding a publication, discovering a dataset)?**
 - o **Objective:** To measure task success rates, efficiency (time/steps) and user satisfaction for core user journeys. This will be achieved by evaluating the platform against its user-centred goals and highlighting areas for improvement in workflow support.
- **RQ3: How do different evaluation methods (HE, MUT, URUT) compare in uncovering usability problems on GoTriple?**
 - o **Objective:** To ensure a comprehensive evaluation by triangulating findings from multiple methods. We want to see which problems are found consistently across methods (indicating severe usability problems),

and which are revealed uniquely by each method, thereby validating the UCQ-FRAME multi-method approach.

- **RQ4: How can the findings from this evaluation be used to refine both the design of GoTriple and the UCQ-FRAME methodology itself?**
 - o **Objective:** Provide actionable recommendations for GoTriple's UX/UI improvements (addressing immediate platform needs) and reflect on the evaluation process to suggest possible refinements to UCQ-FRAME (e.g., improving the framework's tools or procedures based on lessons learned).

By addressing these questions, the report ensures that the evaluation remains focused on user-centred outcomes. The objectives tie in with WP6's emphasis on improving user engagement: **identifying usability pain points (RQ1, RQ2)** is the first step towards improving engagement, and **comparing methods (RQ3)** ensures that we are using the full UCQ-FRAME toolkit to achieve robust results. The final objective **(RQ4)** closes the loop by feeding the findings into **design and methodological improvements**, in keeping with the iterative nature of UCD. Each subsequent section of the report corresponds to these guiding questions - from the chosen methodology to the analysis of the findings and the recommendations derived from them.

4 Evaluation methodology

4.1 Overview of the evaluation approach

To comprehensively evaluate the usability of GoTriple, we used **a triangulated UX evaluation approach, combining heuristic evaluation (HE), moderated usability testing (MUT) (lab and remote) and unmoderated usability testing (URUT)**. This multi-method strategy enabled us to capture both expert-based insights and real user experiences, while ensuring broad coverage of usability problems.

The evaluation was conducted in accordance with the UCQ-FRAME methodology developed in OPERAS-PLUS WP6, which provides a structured and iterative process for user-centred evaluation (Pehar, Juric, & Peša Pavlović, 2024). UCQ-FRAME is aligned with ISO 9241-210 standard (Human-centred design for interactive systems) and ensures that usability evaluations are systematic, evidence-based and actionable.

The evaluation follows the HE, MUT, and URUT methodologies, ensuring a triangulated approach that maximises validity and insight. The combination of these methods mitigates the biases associated with single-method studies and ensures that both broad usability trends and deep user insights are captured.

4.2 Evaluation methods

4.2.1 Heuristic evaluation (HE)

The HE⁵ was conducted as an expert review of the GoTriple platform interface to assess its usability in the context of open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities. This method, introduced by Nielsen & Molich (1990) and formalised in Jakob Nielsen's 10 Usability Heuristics for User Interface Design, is widely used in UX research to efficiently identify usability problems without requiring end-user participation (Nielsen, 1994; Pehar & Pavlović, 2023, p. 99).

The evaluation was carried out in October 2024 independently by **five (5) evaluators**, including UX experts, a quality assurance specialist, a software testing specialist and an open science expert, each of whom assessed the key user flows and functionalities of the platform. All evaluators followed the same structured heuristic evaluation approach, with UX experts bringing deeper usability expertise, while other specialists contributed valuable insights from their respective domains. This combination ensured a comprehensive evaluation that addressed both general usability principles and context-specific research workflows. The evaluation covered critical aspects of the GoTriple user experience, including home page navigation, registration, login/logout and search features, ensuring broad coverage of potential usability violations.

By systematically analysing these features, the evaluation identified numerous usability problems, categorised them by severity and provided actionable recommendations to improve the user experience and interface efficiency. The structured methodology, including detailed findings and prioritised recommendations, supports a systematic approach to usability assessment, ensuring that issues are clearly documented and ready for further validation through user testing.

4.2.1.1 *Scoring criteria: Nielsen's 10 usability heuristics*

To systematically evaluate the usability of GoTriple, the evaluators applied the following 10 usability heuristics:

- **H1: Visibility of System Status** - Ensuring that users receive clear, real-time feedback about system processes and actions.
- **H2: Match between system and real world** - Aligning interface terminology and structure with user expectations and real world conventions.
- **H3: User Control and Freedom** - Providing users with clear ways to undo actions, exit unwanted states, or easily navigate back.
- **H4: Consistency and standards** - Ensuring consistent UI components, terminology and interaction patterns to reduce cognitive load.
- **H5: Error prevention** - Design forms and interactions to minimise user errors through proactive design (e.g. real-time validation, tooltips).
- **H6: Recognising rather than recalling** - Making key information visible and easily accessible to reduce memory dependency.
- **H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use** - support both novice and experienced

⁵ Detailed HE report is available [here](#) (for internal use only).

- users, enabling efficient task completion (e.g. shortcuts, streamlined workflows).
- **H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design** - avoiding visual clutter and prioritising essential interface elements.
- **H9: Helping users detect, diagnose and recover from errors** - Providing clear error messages and easy-to-use troubleshooting guides.
- **H10: Help and Documentation** - Provide easily accessible help resources, tool tips and guidance for new users.

These heuristics were used in the evaluation of across these features: Homepage/Navigation, Sign up, Log in/Log out and Search.

4.2.1.2 *Evaluation process*

Each expert independently navigated the platform, simulating realistic usage scenarios and documenting violations of the usability heuristics. All evaluations were conducted using the English version of GoTriple. The evaluation focused on:

- **Home page and navigation** - Assessing first impressions, clarity of navigation menus and ease of orientation.
- **Searching and filtering** - Assessing search logic, filtering efficiency and feedback visibility.
- **Account management (login/registration)** - Assessing clarity of authentication, form validation and error messages.

Each usability problem identified by an evaluator was linked to a specific violated heuristic, ensuring that the findings were:

- Clearly categorised by heuristic violation.
- Traceable to specific UI elements and interactions.
- Contextualised within expected user behaviour.

For example:

- A missing loading indicator when applying a filter was flagged as a "system status visibility" violation.
- The use of technical jargon in search filter names was identified as a violation of "Match between system and real world".
- The lack of an undo option for inadvertently applied filters was cited under "user control and freedom".

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Evaluator	Affected Area or Related Tasks	Choose Heuristic Violated	Severity Rating	Findings (Description)	Notes and Suggestions	FindingShortName	Upload Screenshots	Screenshot
2	FP	HomeNav	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate problem	The user chooses the "Disciplines" option for Optimise content or structure; Improv		SlowResponse	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
3	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	3 - Severe problem	This issue occurs under the Membership sect Separate issues reporting from Mem		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
4	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	3 - Severe problem	The phrase "Search Resources and Users" a Make explicit what "Resources" refers		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
5	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	The term "Profiles" in the GoTriple numbers a Provide more context around what P		MisleadingLabels	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
6	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	The term "Most Popular" is generic and lacks Clarify the basis of popularity; Addres		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
7	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	The term "Documents" is broad and may cont Add a brief description below the num		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
8	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	Users may expect that all links in the footer (! Use visual cues, such as an icon (e.g		NonStandardLinks	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
9	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	1 - Minor problem	When users search without entering any term Instead of using "valid search term", p		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
10	FP	HomeNav	H3: User Control and Freedom	2 - Moderate problem	The user is unable to proceed or use the plat Fix the link to the Homepage. The bu		RestrictedFreedom	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
11	FP	HomeNav	H3: User Control and Freedom	3 - Severe problem	No feedback for consent actions. Users expe After clicking "Reject all" or "Accept al		RestrictedFreedom	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
12	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor problem	The top color of the overlay message is black Update the overlay to match the color		InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
13	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor problem	The language of the lubenda message might Reword the overlay text to make it mc		ConfusingLabels	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
14	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor problem	The lubenda icon, presented in the bottom r Consider adding a label next to the lu		InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
15	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate problem	GoTriple icon in the top left corner changes e If the logo must change color, ensur		InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
16	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate problem	Inconsistency in terms usage like "Users," " Choose one term (e.g., "Authors") and		MisleadingTerminology	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
17	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate problem	Inconsistency in terms usage like "Resources Choose one term (e.g., "Publications"		MixedTerminology	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
18	FP	HomeNav	H5: Error Prevention	0 - no problem				Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
19	FP	HomeNav	H6: Recognition Rather than Recall	2 - Moderate problem	The recommendations in the "Tailored For Yo Provide users with a brief introduction		HiddenFeatures	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
20	FP	HomeNav	H6: Recognition Rather than Recall	3 - Severe problem	The feature to find collaborators is not easily Add a dedicated section or link on the		HiddenFeatures	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
21	FP	HomeNav	H7: Flexibility and Efficiency of Use	3 - Severe problem	The current search functionality caters only to Include a link or button next to the se		LimitedSearchCuis...	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
22	FP	HomeNav	H8: Aesthetic and Minimalist Design	1 - Minor problem	The inconsistent color scheme between the c Ensure that the consent panel follows		InappropriateDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
23	FP	HomeNav	H9: Help Users Recognize, Diagnose, and Re...	3 - Severe problem	When users enter one or two characters (e.g. Improve the error message by explai		GenericErrorMess...	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
24	FP	HomeNav	H10: Help and Documentation	2 - Moderate problem	Relying on an external platform like Zenodo R implement a dedicated documentation		InaccessibleHelp	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav
25	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate problem	The Sign Up page requires users to accept to Allow users with an existing account t		ConfusingIndicators	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
26	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate problem	The three-step progress indicator is not anym Ensure that the three-step progress r		UnclearProgress	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
27	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	3 - Severe problem	The error message "An error occurred when t The error message should clearly co		MisleadingStatus	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
28	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate problem	The Sign UP confirmation message indicates Include clear next steps (e.g., "Please		HiddenStatus	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
29	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	1 - Minor problem	The term "Operas account" may not be famill Provide a short explanation of what a		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
30	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	The label "Go back to portal" in the sign up c Clarify the label to explicitly state wh		ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
31	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Real World	2 - Moderate problem	The inconsistency in wording between "Sign I Ensure that the language used throug		NonintuitiveNaviga...	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
32	FP	SignUp	H3: User Control and Freedom	1 - Minor problem	The user is unable to easily return to the prev Include a clear, visible "Back" or "Cha		InconsistentControls	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
33	FP	SignUp	H3: User Control and Freedom	2 - Moderate problem	The Sign Up page fails to maintain a clear d For new users: "Follow these three st		ForcedActions	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H
34	FP	SignUp	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate problem			InconsistentSim...	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H

Figure 1: Expert 1 HE checklist - documenting usability violations

4.2.1.3 Severity criteria and expert consensus

In order to prioritise usability problems, each problem was assigned a severity rating based on Nielsen's 0-3 scale:

Table 1. Severity rating scale for usability problems based on Nielsen's 0–3 scale (Nielsen, 1994).

Severity Level	Definition
0 - No usability problem	No usability issues were identified in the area evaluated. ⁶
1 - Minor usability problem	Minor impact on the user experience, unlikely to prevent a task from being completed. These issues are usually cosmetic or minor usability problems that can be easily resolved
2 - Moderate usability problem	Noticeable problems that could affect the user experience but do not prevent the user from completing tasks. These problems require attention and could improve the user experience if fixed.

⁶ The heuristics that were rated 0 = No usability problem was not included in the final analysis because the purpose of the heuristic evaluation is to identify potential usability problems.

3 - Major usability problem

Critical issues that significantly disrupt the user experience or prevent users from completing important tasks. These issues should be prioritized for immediate resolution.

Severity ratings have been determined based on three key factors:

- Frequency - How often the problem is likely to occur (e.g. does it affect all users or only certain cases?).
- Impact - How severely the problem interferes with usability or task completion.
- Persistence - Whether the user can recover easily or whether the problem blocks progress completely.

Each expert initially rated the usability problems independently. This was followed by a session where the evaluators discussed discrepancies and consolidated the results in severity ratings and reached expert consensus on final severity ratings. This consensus rating process ensured that findings were prioritised objectively and not influenced by individual bias.

For example:

- An inconsistent icon design that does not affect user understanding or task completion → Severity 1 (minor usability problem).
- A misleading search filter that causes users to select the wrong options → Severity 3 (severe usability problem).
- The inability to locate the main navigation menu on the home page → Severity 3 (severe usability problem).

The HE provided a structured, expert-led analysis of GoTriple's usability, identifying both high-priority problems and areas for improvement. **The HE method identified 159 usability problems in total. The homepage/navigation had the most usability problems; rated 1-3 (49)**, followed by Sign up function (47), login/logout (34) and search (29). When prioritised by severity, **Search** emerged as the most problematic area in terms of high impact usability problems, despite having fewer problems overall. It contained 4 severe and 5 moderate usability problems. The second most affected area in terms of severity was the Sign Up and Login function.

The findings were integrated with insights from user testing to provide a comprehensive understanding of the usability challenges.

Using Nielsen's heuristics and a structured expert consensus approach, this evaluation enabled a systematic prioritisation of UX issues, providing the basis for evidence-based UX/UI improvements in GoTriple.

4.2.2 Moderated usability testing (MUT)

MUT⁷ was conducted using a hybrid approach, combining face-to-face laboratory

⁷ For a detailed overview of the MUT method see [here](#) (p. 8-11), (for internal use only).

testing and remote testing via video conferencing tool. This approach allowed for controlled observation in a structured environment, while capturing natural user interactions in real-world conditions during remote sessions. The combination of lab and remote testing provided a more comprehensive understanding of usability challenges in different user environments, balancing structured observation with natural user behaviour.

The study followed a formal usability testing process where participants were asked to complete a series of predefined tasks⁸, verbalise their thoughts through a **think-aloud protocol**, and provide feedback on their experience, satisfaction questions in order to collect **satisfaction metrics**, and explain challenges in using GoTriple. The first five tasks were carried out using the English interface, while Task 6 specifically addressed the Croatian interface to assess multilingual usability issues.

4.2.2.1 *Participant selection and profile*

A total of **six (6) participants** were recruited for the study, including three social science researchers, three humanities researchers and two librarians, all based in Croatia. This selection reflected GoTriple's primary user base, ensuring that the usability evaluation was aligned with real-world academic research and information management workflows.

Participants included PhD students, university professors and academic librarians, representing different research roles. All had experience in academic research and regularly used discovery platforms, but none were involved in the development of GoTriple, ensuring that the study captured unbiased end-user experiences.

All six participants tested the Croatian interface (Task 6) to assess multilingual usability aspects, including language consistency and differences in search behaviour.

Previous experience with GoTriple and similar platforms:

- Four participants had never used GoTriple, while two had used it but were not active users.
- Five participants regularly used academic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar on a daily or weekly basis, providing a relevant usability benchmark.
- One participant primarily used alternative full-text search platforms, providing an additional perspective on search behaviour.

This diverse selection of participants ensured that the usability evaluation captured insights from different research workflows and disciplinary backgrounds. By including users with varying levels of experience with discovery platforms, the study was able to identify both common usability challenges and issues specific to different types of academic users.

The usability findings and recommendations derived from this study aim to improve the overall usability of GoTriple, ensuring that the platform effectively meets the needs of both novice and experienced researchers in SSH disciplines.

⁸ Detailed tasks and moderated usability testing plan is available [here](#) (for internal use only).

4.2.2.2 **Lab testing setup**

For the laboratory testing, participants interacted with GoTriple in a controlled environment that allowed for accurate monitoring of user interactions. The test setup included

- **Open Broadcaster Software (OBS)** - An open source, free recording and streaming tool widely used in usability research. OBS was used to:
 - Record high quality video and audio of user sessions for detailed post-test analysis.
 - Stream sessions privately via YouTube, allowing an observer to observe interactions in real time without disturbing the participants.
- YouTube (Private channel streaming) - Sessions were streamed privately, allowing the observer to passively document user interactions, hesitations, comments, and navigation patterns without disrupting the participants' workflow.
- **Moderator**
 - Prepares a **usability testing plan**⁹
 - Runs the session, following the **usability script**¹⁰
 - Reads the **scenario/task** to the participant, observes how the participant performs the task and asks additional questions to gather feedback.
 - Evaluates the task success metrics for each participant
- **Observer Role (note-taker)** - A dedicated observer monitored the live YouTube stream and systematically recorded user behaviour in the findings template. The Observer:
 - Tracked task completion metric.
 - Noted verbalised frustrations and confusion using the think-aloud method.
 - Identified moments of hesitation, navigation errors and unexpected behaviour.

This lab-based approach ensured a high level of observation accuracy, allowing us to identify usability problems that might not have been captured in remote sessions.

Participants signed the Informed consent before conducting the test.¹¹

⁹ The MUT test plan can be found [here](#) (for internal use only).

¹⁰ The MUT script can be found [here](#) (for internal use only).

¹¹ The MUT Informed Consent is available in the [Appendix B](#).

Figure 2. Participant 1 in local lab setup - OBS recording and streaming

4.2.2.3 Remote testing setup

For remote MUT, participants used a preferred video conferencing system (e.g. Google Meet or any other platform with recording capability). The remote testing process involved:

- Participants sharing their screens while completing pre-defined tasks on GoTriple.
- A moderator observing user interactions and guiding the session, following a structured usability testing script.
- Note-taker.
- Recording sessions for later analysis, ensuring that verbal feedback, task completion data and UI interactions were thoroughly documented.

This remote approach simulated near-real-world conditions as users interacted with GoTriple in familiar digital environments, while still providing real-time usability insights through moderator facilitation.

Figure 3. MUT - Participant 3 in remote session (Google Meet) - Identifiable image used with explicit consent of participant

4.2.2.4 Testing process & key tasks

Each MUT session lasted between 60 and 80 minutes, during which participants completed realistic research tasks while thinking aloud.

Key tasks tested

Table 2. Overview of usability testing tasks, scenarios, and objectives in the GoTriple evaluation

Task #	Scenario	Objective
Task 1	Explore the home page	Evaluate clarity of navigation, user orientation and first impressions.
Task 2	Performing a basic search	Evaluate search discoverability, efficiency and presentation of results.
Task 3	Evaluate the relevance of search results	Determine how well search results match user expectations.

Task 4	Narrow search results using filters	Evaluate filter discoverability, usability and feedback effectiveness.
Task 5	Download and analyse a bibliographic record	Evaluate how users access and interpret citation details, metadata and full-text availability
Task 6	Comparison of search functions in Croatian and English interfaces	Testing translation accuracy, language switching usability and multilingual accessibility.

4.2.2.5 *Usability metrics and data collection*

In order to systematically assess usability problems, the following usability metrics were collected

- **Task completion (rated by moderator)**
 - 1 = Task completed with ease
 - 2 = Task completed with difficulty
 - 3 = Task not completed successfully
- **Task level satisfaction (user rating scale: 1-5) (rated by participant)**
 - 1 = Not satisfied at all
 - 5 = Completely satisfied
 - Additional qualitative feedback was gathered through open-ended questions to capture positive and negative impressions.
- **Qualitative user feedback**
- Participants were asked to provide **open-ended feedback** after each task, answering questions such as
 - *What did you like about this experience?*
 - *What didn't you like?*
 - *Do you have any suggestions for improvement?*
- **Observed usability problems (assigned by researcher)**

A severity rating scale is defined for each identified usability problem:

- 1 – "*Cosmetic problem*" - It is not necessary to remove the problem, unless we have time

- 2 - *Minor usability problem* - Low priority problem, it needs to be removed, the user can still complete the task successfully, but with difficulties
- 3 - *Severe usability problem* - A major usability problem due to which the user is unable to complete the task, a high priority problem, it is important to remove it

Collecting usability metrics¹² together with qualitative user insights (verbal feedback, observed frustrations) enabled a well-rounded usability evaluation that went beyond numerical scores to identify actionable usability improvements.

The moderated usability test identified **30 severe and moderate problems**, including **12 severe** and **18 moderate usability problems**, across **six tasks**: searching, assessing the relevance of search results, narrowing results using filters, downloading and analysing bibliographic records, and comparing search functions in the Croatian language interface.

Figure 4: Screenshot of all MUT recordings - documentation of usability test sessions conducted in laboratory and remote environments

By integrating lab-based and remote testing, this hybrid MUT approach provided a rich dataset that captured usability problems in both controlled and near-real-world settings. This comprehensive assessment of GoTriple's usability problems ensured that recommended improvements were based on structured observations and actual user behaviour, improving the overall user experience and accessibility of the platform.

¹² For overview of the collected metrics, see Moderated usability report (Chapter Performance data, from p.19) available [here](#) (for internal use only)

4.2.3 Unmoderated usability test (URUT)

URUT was conducted as the final phase of the GoTriple usability evaluation, providing further validation of findings from HE and MUT. While previous evaluations relied on expert review and direct observation, URUT captured task performance metrics, navigation paths and usability perceptions, allowing for a broader, data-driven assessment of user interactions with the platform.

Unlike MUT, where facilitators guide participants, URUT requires users to complete tasks independently, reflecting natural user behaviour and real-world decision-making processes. Conducted remotely using [Loop11](#), a usability testing platform that supports task-based analysis, success rate tracking, clickstream recording and survey integration, URUT provided additional insight into how researchers interact with GoTriple in their own environment, without external influence. This method provided a structured usability evaluation while maintaining a broad participant reach, ensuring that quantitative usability data was complemented by qualitative user feedback. For more details on the selection of Loop11, see Appendix E.

URUT was designed to evaluate the usability of GoTriple in an unmoderated environment, focusing on ease of navigation, user satisfaction and task success rates. In addition to identifying usability problems, it aimed to validate findings from previous evaluations with a larger and more diverse sample of participants. The study captured task success rates, clickstream data and response times, and included post-test surveys including the UEQ-S, SUS and NPS to assess perceived usability, user experience and loyalty. Open-ended feedback provided further insight into user frustrations, expectations and workflow efficiency.

By incorporating URUT into the evaluation process, the study ensured a comprehensive, triangulated understanding of GoTriple's usability. It combined the depth of expert and direct user testing with validation on a larger group of users, providing a well-rounded assessment of both systematic usability flaws and real-world user challenges.

4.2.3.1 *Participant selection & sample size*

The initial study plan was to recruit 30+ participants to ensure statistical robustness. However, by the time the report was finalised, **25 participants** had completed the test. The test remains open for one month to allow for additional responses after the report deadline.

Participants were selected to represent GoTriple's core user base, ensuring coverage of diverse SSH researchers. The inclusion of a larger sample size in URUT aimed to validate usability trends identified in previous evaluations.

4.2.3.2 *Test procedure & key tasks*

URUT followed a structured, task-based evaluation covering four key research tasks, which were aligned with previous usability studies:

Table 3. Overview of usability testing tasks, scenarios, and objectives.

Task #	Scenario	Objective
Task 1	Exploring the home page	Assessing clarity of navigation, user orientation and first impressions.
Task 2	Searching for publications	Evaluating search discoverability, efficiency and relevance of search results.
Task 3	Apply filters to refine search results	Test the usability, visibility and efficiency of search refinement options.
Task 4	Exploring a publication's metadata and citation options	Evaluating the clarity and accessibility of bibliographic details and citation functionalities.

While URUT focused primarily on quantitative data collection, it also incorporated qualitative elements such as optional screen and audio recordings, navigation path tracking and user comments. This ensured a deeper understanding of usability issues that could not be captured by numerical metrics alone.

4.2.3.3 **Usability metrics and data collection**

To ensure a comprehensive usability evaluation, the following key usability metrics were collected:

- Task-based performance metrics
 - Task Success Rate - Measured by the completion or failure of pre-defined objectives.
 - Time on Task - The time taken by each participant to complete a given task.
 - Task Completion (rated by researchers)
 - 1 = Task completed with ease
 - 2 = Task completed with difficulty
 - 3 = Task not completed successfully

- This was assessed using screen recordings and clickstream data where available.

Figure 5. URUT Task 2 - Searching for publications: Clickstream navigation and task success rate

- User reported metrics
 - Ease of Use Ratings - Participants rated the ease of use of each task on a 1-5 Likert scale.
 - User-identified usability problems - Captured via open-ended post-task survey questions.
 - Suggestions for Improvement - Participants provided feedback on potential improvements to the functionality and usability of the platform.
- Severity Assessment & Problem Prioritisation
 - Severity Rating Scale - Each usability problem identified was assigned a severity rating:
 - 1 – *"Cosmetic problem"* - It is not necessary to remove the problem, unless we have time.
 - 2 - *Minor usability problem* - Low priority problem, it needs to be removed, the user can still complete the task successfully, but with difficulties.

- 3 - *Severe usability problem* - A major usability problem due to which the user is unable to complete the task, a high priority problem, it is important to remove it.
 - This process required researchers to qualitatively analyse screen recordings, identify unreported or partially reported usability problems and validate user feedback.
- Post-test UX & satisfaction surveys
 - Standard UX evaluation tools were used to assess the overall usability perception:
 - **SUS** - A standardised benchmarking tool that measures perceived usability.
 - **UEQ-S** - Measures the pragmatic and hedonic quality of UX.
 - **NPS** - Assessed user/customer loyalty based on the likelihood to recommend GoTriple.

4.2.3.4 ***URUT execution & technical considerations***

Testing platform & tool configuration

URUT was conducted using Loop11, a usability testing tool designed for remote user evaluations. The platform provided:

- Automated task tracking - Monitored user performance via target URLs, clickstream tracking and screen recordings.
- Survey integration - Enabled the collection of quantitative and qualitative feedback in a structured format.
- Audio & video recording (optional) - Participants were able to share screen/audio to provide contextual insight into usability challenges.

Figure 6. Loop 11 modes of response - screen, audio and text based participation in URUT

Methodological trade-offs

- Flexibility of screen & audio sharing - Some users were reluctant to enable screen/audio recording. In such cases, estimates of task difficulty were inferred from navigation paths, response times, and user-reported problems. This approach is a methodological shortcoming because sometimes it is not possible to reliably resolve the unclear circumstances related to the usability problems they encountered. This compromise is done because more detailed qualitative insights were already collected in moderated usability testing.

- Consideration of fatigue - Given the 30-40 minute session length, certain tasks were omitted from the moderated phase in order to reduce cognitive load and respondent fatigue.

These methodological decisions ensured inclusivity while maintaining data validity, striking a balance between user comfort and research rigour.

URUT provided further validation of findings from heuristic evaluation and moderated usability testing, allowing us to:

- Confirm previously identified usability problems with wider user involvement.
- Quantify usability metrics such as task success rates, ease of use and overall satisfaction.
- Gain new insights from self-reported usability challenges and open-ended participant feedback.

By integrating structured task assessments, UX satisfaction surveys (SUS, UEQ-S, NPS) and optional screen/audio recordings, URUT complemented the qualitative insights from previous phases while providing statistical validation of usability problems.

URUT results are triangulated with heuristic and moderated testing results, ensuring that prioritised usability recommendations are based on robust multi-method validation.

4.3 Ethical considerations

This evaluation was conducted in accordance with ethical best practice, ensuring that participants' rights, privacy and data security were fully protected. The ethical principles outlined in UCQ-FRAME and GDPR were strictly adhered to throughout the study.

Key ethical considerations included:

- **Informed consent:** All participants received detailed information about the purpose, methods and data use of the study prior to participation. A standard consent form was used to ensure transparency, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequence.
 - For Informed consent in MUT, see Appendix B.
 - For informed consent in URUT, see Appendix C.
- **Privacy and anonymity:** No personally identifiable information was stored in the test results. In URUT, screen recordings only captured platform interactions, while in MUT webcam recordings were securely stored with explicit participant consent.
- **Data security:** All data collected was securely stored and will only be retained for the time necessary, in accordance with the OPERAS data retention policy. Following analysis, sensitive data will be permanently deleted in accordance with GDPR guidelines.
- **Voluntary participation:** Participation was entirely voluntary and participants

were fully informed that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. Recruitment was conducted in a way that ensured there were no power imbalances (e.g. avoiding hierarchical dependencies between researchers and participants), and no incentives or rewards were offered for participation.

- **Minimising discomfort:** The study was designed to avoid stress or discomfort by emphasising that the system, not the participants, was being evaluated. If users encountered difficulties, moderators provided assistance as necessary to avoid undue frustration. Since this is not possible in URUT, to support participants an instructional video was produced along with detailed textual instructions for each task to guide them through the setup and testing process, reducing uncertainty and technical difficulties (<https://youtu.be/VA47syHMz8k>).

By adhering to strict ethical standards, this evaluation ensured participant trust, research transparency and compliance with institutional and legal guidelines, thereby strengthening the integrity and reliability of the findings.

5 Findings & recommendations

5.1 Overview of usability problems identified

The evaluation of the GoTriple platform identified key usability problems across HE, MUT and URUT, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of usability issues. While the HE revealed inconsistencies in the interface design and systematic usability flaws, these results were validated and extended through MUT by capturing real user frustrations and inefficiencies. The data from the URUT is still being collected, but the first results are consistent with the findings from the two previous phases of the usability evaluation.

Below we categorise the usability problems by severity and key areas affected, and provide recommendations for improvement.

5.1.1 High severity usability problems (Critical/Major)

These issues significantly interfered with task completion or caused major frustration and should be prioritised for resolution.

5.1.1.1 Search functionality & filtering issues

Identified by: HE, MUT and URUT

- The HE identified structural problems with the search functionality, including a lack of advanced filtering options, difficulties in customising the search, and inefficient search refinement.
- MUT validated these findings, with some users expressing confusion about specific filters (redundancy in terminology, such as “text” vs. “article”). Some users struggled with the search functionality and the logic of the filters.
- URUT confirms the importance of incorporating specific redesign

recommendations. For example, participants strongly support enabling advanced searches with multiple search fields.

Effect on UX: Search usability is a major problem affecting task success rates and user satisfaction. Users had some problems with query formulation, filtering options and relevance of search results.

Limited search & lack of advanced query options (Severity 3)

- **Findings:** Users were unable to refine the search across multiple fields (e.g. abstract, title, keywords). Boolean operators were required but not visible.
- **Effect on UX:** Search was perceived ineffective, and users lacked control.
- **Recommendation:** Implement advanced search options, including field-based search (e.g. filter by title, author, abstract).

Figure 7. Recommendation: Implement advanced search options

Filter usability and discoverability issues (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Some users could not find or understand filters (language, subject, publication date). Filtering logic was unclear and sometimes missing filters (i.e. filter for “information science” discipline is missing)
- **Effect on UX:** Some users struggled to narrow search results effectively. This subgroup of users, based on additional data from the URUT, also had difficulties in the previous search task. Overall, the filters were easy to apply for the majority of participants.
- **Recommendation:** Improve clarity of filter labels, introduce tooltips and group filters logically. Prominently display active filters. Implement the possibility to exclude or include more than one filter at a time.

Figure 8. Recommendation: Implement the ability to exclude or include more than one filter at a time.

Lack of feedback when no results are returned (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Empty search results left users unsure of what to do next.
- **Recommendation:** Provide suggestions such as "Did you mean...?" or offer related search results.

Inconsistent handling of special characters (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Searches with diacritics (e.g. ž, é) returned inconsistent or incorrect results.
- **Recommendation:** Implement character normalisation to ensure accurate search functionality.

5.1.1.2 Navigation & homepage structure

Identified by: HE, MUT and URUT

- HE revealed confusing terminology and navigation structure issues.
- MUT revealed that some of the homepage features were unclear to users (Membership & Data services f.e.)
- URUT revealed that most of the participants generally agreed that the platform's purpose is clear and that the terminology is mostly understandable. However, participants who feel unclear about what the platform offers also rate the system as less usable (UEQ-S Pragmatic scale, SUS), less engaging, and less exciting (UEQ-S Hedonic scale). Therefore, it is important to consider their feedback.

Effect on UX: The home page lacked clear guidance and navigation elements and this was confusing for some users.

Unclear home page orientation (Severity 3)

- **Findings:** Users were not sure where to start. "Recommended" content lacked explanation.
- **Recommendation:** Add a clear introductory statement and a guided onboarding experience.

Figure 9. Recommendation: explain why "Tailored for you" is recommended

Confusing terminology in menu labels (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Labels such as 'Membership' and 'Data Services' were unclear.
- **Recommendation:** Revise menu terminology to align with user expectations.

[Home](#) [About GoTRIPLE](#) [Membership](#) [Disciplines](#) [Data services](#)

Figure 10. Recommendation: Explain what "Membership" and "Data Services" mean

Inconsistent navigation & lack of feedback (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Users had difficulty identifying their current page due to a lack of active status indicators.
- **Recommendation:** Introduce breadcrumbs and highlight active sections in the

navigation bar.

5.1.1.3 **Language switching & multilingual support**

Identified by: HE and MUT

- HE highlighted issues with inconsistent translations and hidden language switching mechanisms.
- MUT found that users did not like untranslated or poorly translated UI elements.

Effect on UX: Multilingual features were unintuitive, reducing accessibility for non-English users.

Croatian interface translation issues (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Some UI elements remained in English, breaking immersion for native Croatian users.
- **Recommendation:** Conduct a full localisation review and ensure consistency of translations.

Figure 11. Recommendation: Improve translation (in this example, Croatian language)

5.1.1.4 **Bibliographic records & citation functions**

- Identified through: HE, MUT and URUT
 - HE identified missing metadata, unclear full-text access and lack of export options.
 - MUT confirmed that users had difficulty finding full-text links on the bibliographic record page (sometimes there was no any link, even after applying a full text link). Users would like that list of results and

bibliographic record units show citation for each record (like known databases)

- URUT showed that most users strongly demand the addition of quick citation downloads in APA, MLA, and other styles. They also show significant interest in additional export options, in RIS and similar formats.

Effect on UX: Users had difficulty understanding metadata and accessing citation options.

Missing or incomplete metadata (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Important fields such as author affiliations, page numbers, DOI, citation counts and open access indicators were missing or unclear.
- **Recommendation:** Ensure that metadata is complete for each bibliographic record. Provide more options for export (such as export in different citation styles)

Figure 12. Recommendation: Expand export options beyond BibTeX and JSON to include APA, Harvard, MLA, Chicago, and IEEE, improving integration with reference managers like Zotero

Article English ID: <ftzenodo:oa:zenodo.org:7654542> - DOI: <10.5281/zenodo.7654542> Where these data come from ⓘ

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INNOVATION IN EDUCATION

Authors: [Prof. Pragnya Jitendra Nehete & Prof. Saugat Das](#)

Publication Date: 2022-06-24

Last GoTriple update: 2023-04-29

Provider: Base

License: Undefined

Conditions of Access: Open Access

Disciplines: Education Management

Keywords: Research Trends EDM Multiple Intelligence Framework Smart Teaching Assistant System E-Learning

TRIPLE Vocabulary tags: Artificial Intelligence Education Intellect Learning Manners and customs Progress Risk

Switch tags language: English

[View document page](#)
[Annotate document page](#)
[Export](#)
 Share [f](#) [in](#) [t](#)

Figure 13. Recommendation: Extend bibliographic record data, e.g. publication title, pages, DOI, type of licence, affiliation, type of document, etc.

Difficulty accessing full text (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Users had difficulty finding full-text access links, leading to confusion (when filter “full text is applied)
- **Recommendation:** Add the green button "Full text option" button to the main results list and to the right of the full bibliographic record screen. Improve visual prominence of download or external access links.

[Ways of modernization of informational training for university students](#)

Fomina N. A., Ivanova D. S., Somova M.V. +1 author

2021-01-01

The article substantiates the need for informatization of education in general, and higher professional education in particular, requiring the modernization of forms, methods and content of information training of students in the light of the implementation of the program “Digital Economy...

[Full text option](#)

Figure 14. Recommendation: Add the green button "Full text option" button to the main results list and to the right of the full bibliographic record screen

5.1.1.5 Account registration & authentication issues

Identified by: HE, MUT

- HE highlighted problems with the registration process, unclear password

requirements and lack of feedback on errors.

Effect on UX: The registration and login process were confusing, resulting in user abandonment.

Confusing login flow & lack of clear instructions (Severity 3)

- **Findings:** Evaluators were unsure what an OPERAS account was and how to proceed.
- **Recommendation:** Add contextual help messages during registration.

Inadequate password error messages (Severity 3)

- **Finding:** Users received generic error messages that did not explain how to resolve the issues.
- **Recommendation:** Provide real-time password validation with clear requirements.

Authentication required

You can create an OPERAS account using your ORCID , GOOGLE or EGI account if you already have one or create one directly.

Login or Mail

Password

Check my last logins

Connect

Reset my password Create an account

Go to portal

Figure 15. Recommendation: Provide a clear process for password requirements and validation

5.1.2 Structured and actionable recommendations

Table 4 presents **structured and actionable UX recommendations** for improving the GoTriple. Each recommendation is categorised based on key areas of improvement,

assigned a priority level and evaluated in terms of estimated effort. The roadmap phase indicates when each change should be implemented, ensuring a clear and phased approach to usability improvements.

Table 4. Usability improvement roadmap: prioritised recommendations and implementation effort

Category	Recommendation	Priority Level	Estimated Effort	Roadmap Phase
Search & Filtering	Implement field-based search (title, author, keywords).	High	H	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Introduce autocomplete suggestions for query formulation.	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Improve filter visibility & persistent display.	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Clarify filtering logic	High	L	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Provide feedback for empty search results (e.g., "Did you mean...?").	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Ensure proper handling of diacritics & special characters in search.	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
Navigation & Homepage	Move GoTriple description to the top of the homepage.	High	L	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Improve clarity of recommended content section.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
	Standardize menu labels (rename "Tools" to "Vocabulary & API").	High	L	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Ensure consistent navigation across all pages (fix missing active states).	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Implement breadcrumbs for navigation clarity.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements

Multilingual Support	Make language selector more visible & intuitive.	High	L	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Fully translate Croatian interface (fix missing translations).	High	H	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Preserve user context when switching languages.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
Bibliographic Records & Metadata	Ensure all bibliographic records include title, author affiliations, DOI, and citation data.	High	H	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Improve visibility of full-text access (clear download links).	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Implement citation export options (APA, MLA, RIS etc.).	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
Authentication & Account Management	Clarify the purpose of OPERAS ID during sign-up.	High	L	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Improve error messages & provide clear password validation feedback.	High	M	Phase 1 – Immediate Fixes
	Introduce OAuth login options (Google, ORCID).	Moderate	H	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
Performance & Feedback Mechanisms	Implement loading indicators for search & save operations.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
	Add "Success" messages for saved searches & actions.	Moderate	L	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
Help & Onboarding	Introduce tooltips & quick guides for first-time users.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
	Implement a guided tour for key features.	Moderate	H	Phase 3 – Future Enhancements

UI & Layout Improvements	Adjust filter panel layout to balance search results visibility.	Moderate	M	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
	Standardize button placements & UI elements for consistency.	Moderate	L	Phase 2 – UX/UI Refinements
	Improve spacing & readability of bibliographic records.	Low	L	Phase 3 – Future Enhancements

5.2 Strengths and positive aspects of GoTriple

While the evaluation identified key usability problems, it also highlighted several **positive aspects of the GoTriple platform**. The results from HE and MUT show that users and evaluators appreciated several aspects of GoTriple's design, functionality and usability.

Some of the positive findings of the HE were that evaluators considered that **the design** is nice and clean, they liked the **colours** of the interface and **minimalist and aesthetic design**.

Some of the positive findings of the MUT were that GoTriple has nice **visualisation features** (such as “knowledge map” and “streamgraph”). Participants from the MUT session also liked the possibility to visualize **the publication dates in a graph**. Also, some participants said that **“Related projects”** are a nice feature, and it was innovative. Also, similar to this, they found the feature **“from the same author”** a valuable option. Participants also liked **the coloured tags in the bibliographic record**: keywords, disciplines and TRIPLE Vocabulary tags.

These strengths contribute to a strong foundation for future usability refinements and improved user engagement.

5.2.1 User interface and visual design

GoTriple was consistently praised for its aesthetic and minimalist design, which contributed to a positive first impression and ease of navigation. Three out of five HE evaluators specifically noted the clean, well-structured layout and its contribution to the overall usability. MUT participants also highlighted that the interface was visually appealing and in line with modern UX expectations for research discovery platforms.

5.2.2 Search functionality and features

Search-related features were among the most positively received aspects of GoTriple:

- Simple and effective search options that users found intuitive.
- Visualisations
- Good visibility of system status while searching, with no major usability problems identified.

- The possibility to copy search queries, making it easier for users to efficiently refine and customise their searches.
- Useful language filtering options, which were particularly well received by multilingual users.
- The "related projects" feature, which enhances the search by linking users to additional relevant content.

Figure 16. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: the possibility to copy search queries

Figure 17. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: graphical visualisation of the publication date filter

Figure 18. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: visualisations

5.2.3 Content organisation and accessibility

Participants found several content-related features particularly useful:

- The "View PDF" option, which allows easy access to documents.
- Keywords, disciplines and TRIPLE Vocabulary tags, which were effectively implemented and provided meaningful links between content.
- The ability to find both projects and authors, supporting broader research discovery beyond publications.

Figure 19. One of the positive features are the coloured tags in the bibliographic record: disciplines, keywords, TRIPLE Vocabulary tags

Figure. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: related projects and authors

Figure 20. One of the positive features of the Go Triple platform: related projects and authors

5.2.4 User account management and system reliability

GoTriple performed well in terms of technical reliability, particularly for the 50

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account-related features:

- The registration process was well structured, with four out of five experts from the heuristic evaluation, reporting no significant usability concerns related to recognition rather than recall.
- The login/logout process showed robust error prevention, with four out of five experts confirming its reliability.

5.2.5 Navigation and information architecture

Participants particularly appreciated aspects of GoTriple's navigation and information structure:

- A clean and minimalist homepage design, which was well received by both HE and MUT.
- A well-structured navigation system that supported easy access to the platform's core functionality.

These findings suggest that GoTriple successfully implements several key usability principles, particularly in the areas of aesthetic design, search functionality, content organisation and technical stability. While there are areas that require refinement, the positive aspects provide a strong foundation for further UX and usability improvements. Future developments should build on these strengths while addressing the key usability challenges identified in the evaluation.

6 Insights for UCQ-FRAME

The usability evaluation of GoTriple has not only provided important insights for **improving the platform itself**, but also serves as **a test case for refining the UCQ-FRAME**. As a structured approach to evaluating the usability and quality of OPERAS services, **UCQ-FRAME needs to be adapted to the practical realities of SSH research platforms - particularly in terms of methodological best practice**, participant recruitment and the integration of usability findings into platform development.

This evaluation followed a triangulated approach, ensuring that both qualitative and quantitative insights were gained from different evaluation methods. Each method contributed unique strengths and limitations, highlighting areas where UCQ-FRAME can be further refined to improve future usability evaluations.

A key challenge in this evaluation was **participant recruitment**, particularly within the SSH research community. The reliance on ad hoc recruitment methods proved to be resource intensive, highlighting the need for a structured and sustainable research panel. While UCQ-FRAME does not currently suggest specific participant recruitment strategies, this evaluation suggests that incorporating structured recruitment mechanisms - possibly using an existing OPERAS service such as VERA - could improve the long-term feasibility of user research studies in SSH contexts.

In addition, the evaluation highlighted the importance of **integrating expert-led usability assessments earlier in the development lifecycle**. While HE was effective in identifying usability flaws, it was also resource intensive, requiring an average of 14 hours per expert to complete. This highlights the need for strategic timing, embedding expert reviews in early design and prototyping phases to anticipate usability problems prior to full platform deployment.

URUT also presented challenges in terms of **participant burden and technological constraints**. The requirement for screen/audio sharing and browser extensions discouraged some participants from engaging, while the test protocol was cognitively demanding, leading to participant fatigue and potential dropout. These findings suggest that UCQ-FRAME should provide clearer guidance on the balance between test depth and participant burden, to ensure that usability evaluations remain both rigorous and manageable.

Finally, an overarching challenge was the **translation of usability findings into actionable, trackable improvements**. While usability problems were documented with clear recommendations, ensuring a structured and harmonised communication process remains essential to prioritise and implement changes effectively. Given the constraints of resource availability and project-based funding cycles, major interventions may not always be immediately feasible. UCQ-FRAME could benefit from a **structured issue tracking mechanism** to ensure that findings are not only documented, but also systematically assessed, addressed and validated through a formal feedback loop. A clearer alignment between usability evaluation and

development planning would help to optimise efforts and improve the long-term sustainability of platform improvements.

The following sections outline specific areas where UCQ-FRAME can be refined based on the lessons learned from this evaluation. These refinements aim to strengthen methodological guidance, participant recruitment strategies and the integration of usability findings into platform development, ensuring that UCQ-FRAME remains a practical, scalable and actionable framework for assessing user-centred quality in OPERAS services.

6.1 **Strengthening UCQ-FRAME's multi-method evaluation strategy**

A key takeaway from this review is that **no single usability evaluation method is sufficient on its own**. HE efficiently uncovers interface-level usability flaws, but does not capture real-world user struggles or overall UX perceptions. MUT provides qualitative depth, but is resource intensive. URUT provides quantitative validation, but lacks direct user interaction to explore motivations behind behaviour.

Findings from HE, MUT and URUT

- HE identified early usability violations, including navigation inconsistencies, unclear system feedback, and problems with filtering logic. This method did not capture how users interpret search results or bibliographic metadata.
- MUT uncovered deeper usability problems that experts alone could not anticipate, such as cognitive overload in search results, confusion with multilingual interfaces, frustration with incomplete metadata.
- URUT validated these issues at scale, in particular through user ratings of the redesign recommendations importance, and by examining how tasks specific ratings and metrics correlate with the overall UX perceptions measured with UEQ-S, SUS and NPS. URUT's UEQ-S and NPS results showed the importance of pragmatic or usability qualities in ensuring user loyalty.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Embed a structured hybrid evaluation model that combines HE for early problem identification, MUT for in-depth analysis, and URUT for validation at scale.**
- **Ensure iterative testing at all stages of development, rather than relying solely on post-deployment evaluations.**
- **Balance usability testing with UX metrics by incorporating subjective user perceptions (e.g. efficiency, reliability, confidence in search results, and intuitiveness of navigation) into usability assessments.**

By refining UCQ-FRAME to promote multi-method usability and UX evaluation, future assessments can better capture both functional usability problems and broader user experience challenges. A structured, iterative approach will ensure that SSH research platforms remain aligned with user needs over time.

6.2 Adapting heuristics for research platforms

SSH research platforms differ from general-purpose platforms in their use cases, multilingual complexity, and academic search behaviour. While standard usability heuristics (e.g., Nielsen's principles) provide a strong foundation, they do not fully address research-specific needs such as metadata clarity, citation handling, and search transparency.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Extend the heuristic criteria to assess research-specific UX factors such as multilingual support, research workflow efficiency, and metadata clarity.**
- **Incorporate UX expectations into heuristic evaluations, including user confidence in search relevance, filter transparency, and research-specific navigation needs.**
- **Ensure that heuristic evaluations incorporate both interface-level usability flaws and broader UX concerns such as perceived reliability and efficiency.**

By refining heuristics to capture SSH-specific usability and UX challenges, UCQ-FRAME can help evaluators better assess platforms such as GoTriple in a way that aligns with researchers' real-world workflows.

6.3 Improve usability problem prioritisation and tracking

A recurring problem in usability evaluations is that documenting problems does not guarantee their resolution. While problems were thoroughly identified, prioritisation and tracking remained ad hoc, making it difficult to ensure that fixes were implemented and validated in subsequent iterations.

Findings from HE, MUT and URUT:

- HE identified a high number of usability problems, but some had limited real-world impact, highlighting the need for better prioritisation.
- MUT provided critical context on which usability problems were truly hindering user workflow, distinguishing between severe problems and minor inefficiencies.
- URUT's UX scores revealed that some usability fixes might not necessarily improve overall UX, highlighting the need for continuous post-fix validation.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Implement a structured severity/impact framework that ensures issues are prioritised based on task failure risk, user frustration and workflow disruption.**
- **Establish a usability problem tracking mechanism to ensure that each identified issue has an assigned owner, resolution steps and follow-up validation.**

- **Encourage post-implementation UX validation, measuring whether fixes actually improve usability and user perception.**

By ensuring that usability problems are not only documented, but systematically addressed and re-evaluated, UCQ-FRAME can help OPERAS services sustain long-term usability and UX improvements.

6.4 **Exploring the feasibility of sustainable participant recruitment and research panels**

One of the most resource-intensive aspects of the GoTriple usability evaluation was **participant recruitment**. The process required significant effort to ensure a representative user base of SSH researchers. While recruitment was mostly successful, the reliance on ad hoc strategies presented challenges in terms of efficiency, scalability and long-term sustainability.

As SSH research infrastructures expand, UCQ-FRAME should consider more structured recruitment mechanisms that reduce reliance on one-off outreach efforts. A dedicated research panel could support long-term usability studies by providing

- A stable pool of SSH researchers willing to participate in future evaluations.
- A more efficient recruitment workflow, reducing the need for last-minute outreach.
- Greater diversity in the selection of participants, ensuring that findings reflect a wider range of user experiences.

Lessons from HE, MUT and URUT:

- HE was independent of recruitment challenges, but could benefit from earlier input from SSH researchers in the development of heuristics.
- MUT required intensive co-ordination to secure participants with diverse research backgrounds, which slowed down the timetable. (country, language bias)!
- URUT was scalable but faced drop-out and engagement issues, particularly where technical barriers (e.g. browser extensions) were involved.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Encourage exploring structured recruitment models, such as research panels or pre-registered participant pools.**
- **Encourage existing initiatives (e.g. VERA) to explore facilitating participant recruitment, recognising that current capacity may be limited.**
- **Develop best practice for recruitment efficiency, ensuring that evaluators allocate sufficient time and resources to participant recruitment.**

While UCQ-FRAME cannot prescribe a specific recruitment strategy, it should encourage long-term solutions that make usability testing more scalable and efficient.

Exploring research panels, institutional partnerships, and structured participant engagement strategies will help reduce recruitment barriers in future evaluations.

6.5 **Overcoming technological barriers and test setup efficiency in URUT studies**

A key challenge in URUT was the high dropout rate at the start of the study, largely due to participants' reluctance to install browser extensions for screen/audio/video recording. In addition, while remote usability testing is expected to capture natural usage across devices, the evaluation revealed that only two participants completed the URUT on a mobile device. This raises concerns about both the intuitiveness of Loop11 for mobile testing and the mobile responsiveness of the GoTriple platform itself.

To mitigate the barriers posed by complex technical setups, we adapted our URUT testing approach by offering three different test modes to accommodate participants' preferences and privacy concerns:

- Full screen recording and microphone - capturing verbal think-aloud feedback alongside real-time interaction.
- Partial screen recording without microphone - replacing verbalisation with open-ended written responses to capture participant reflections.
- No screen/audio sharing, only open-ended questions - focusing solely on self-reported usability experiences to ensure inclusivity for privacy-conscious participants.

This flexibility was essential to reduce attrition and ensure that participants could still contribute to the study even if they were reluctant to share screen/audio data.

Findings from URUT:

- High dropout rate at baseline - many users refused to install the Loop11 browser extension, citing privacy concerns, reluctance to change browser settings, or setup difficulties.
- The setup process felt intrusive, especially compared to the more familiar screen sharing experience of Zoom or Google Meet.
- Mobile participation was unexpectedly low - only two participants completed the URUT on a mobile device, even though many researchers frequently access platforms via mobile browsers.
- Loop11 was not intuitive enough for mobile usability testing, which may have discouraged participants from trying the test on their phones.
- The GoTriple platform itself was not fully optimised for mobile - responsive design, and this may have further discouraged mobile-based interactions.

UCQ FRAME refinements:

- **Prioritise frictionless, browser-based recording solutions that do not require extensions or software installation.**

- Offer alternative test modes - ensure participants can choose between full, partial or unrecorded participation, reducing barriers to engagement.
- Improve pre-test onboarding with clear, reassuring instructions on why recording is necessary, what will be recorded and how the data will be handled.
- Ensure that testing tools support mobile-friendly usability testing - evaluators should check that platforms such as Loop11 work smoothly on different smartphones and tablets.
- Assess mobile usability more explicitly in UCQ-FRAME evaluations, ensuring that platforms being tested, such as GoTriple, are responsive and fully functional across devices.

This challenge highlights an important methodological trade-off in remote usability testing: ensuring a smooth, privacy-conscious setup while capturing realistic, multi-device user behaviour. UCQ-FRAME should emphasise flexible, low-barrier testing solutions, while ensuring that research platforms are designed for seamless mobile usability, not just desktop interactions. In addition, the provision of multiple testing modes in URUT proved valuable in enabling more users to participate despite privacy concerns or technical limitations. Future studies should continue to balance participant flexibility with the need for comprehensive usability data.

6.6 Preparation and pilot testing of usability studies: Managing cognitive load and fatigue

A key lesson from the GoTriple usability evaluation is that thorough preparation and pilot testing are essential to ensure that usability studies produce reliable evidence. Pilot testing was carried out for all methods (HE, MUT and URUT), allowing evaluators to refine, for example, test instruments, scenarios and rating scales prior to full deployment:

- In HE, a structured scoring sheet was developed and refined to ensure consistency in identifying usability violations.
- In MUT, usability tasks, scenarios and data collection instruments were informed by the HE findings, with pre-testing helping to refine question clarity, task feasibility and session flow.
- URUT identified key challenges, particularly around participant fatigue, cognitive overload and technical barriers, suggesting that even more rigorous pre-testing could have helped to mitigate these issues.

Although usability testing tools and methods have been piloted and refined, the full studies still faced **participant fatigue** and **dropout risks** due to demanding tasks and setup complexity, particularly in URUT. This highlights the need for even more iterative testing cycles, with greater attention to technological compatibility, participant burden and workflow efficiency.

Findings from HE, MUT and URUT:

- HE successfully piloted a structured scoring sheet to ensure consistency across expert reviews. However, as HE relied on experts rather than real end users, cognitive load was not a major issue.
- MUT pre-tested the task design and session structure to ensure that the usability scenarios were well planned and informed by HE's findings. However, during full-scale testing, some participants struggled with ambiguous task instructions, requiring additional clarification from the moderators. Variability in task completion approaches and direct participant feedback suggested that further iterative pilot testing could have helped to refine task clarity, reduce misinterpretation and improve consistency of user responses.
- URUT showed the most participant frustration, reinforcing that tool selection, task refinement, and simplicity of setup should be further optimised in the pre-testing phase. In order to facilitate participant onboarding, a short demo video (YouTube: <https://youtu.be/VA47syHMz8k>) was created explaining how to install and conduct the study using the Loop11 browser extension. However, despite these efforts, many participants still dropped out at the entry stage, suggesting that video guidance alone was not sufficient to mitigate technical complexity, privacy concerns and perceived intrusiveness.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Formalise pre-testing as a required step in usability studies, ensuring that**
 - **Task clarity is tested through multiple pilot rounds to eliminate confusion.**
 - **Rating scales are validated for consistency, reducing misinterpretation.**
 - **Test environments are optimised for accessibility, ensuring seamless participation.**
- **Cognitive load is assessed before full studies are launched, focusing on:**
 - **Task complexity & effort level, avoiding unnecessary cognitive load.**
 - **Session structuring, ensuring manageable test durations.**
 - **Smooth onboarding, reducing participant frustration during set-up.**
- **Improving the usability of usability testing tools, ensuring that:**
 - **Platforms such as Loop11, Maze and Lookback work intuitively and without unnecessary setup friction.**
 - **Mobile usability testing is explicitly considered, addressing responsiveness issues that may deter participation.**
- **Refine consensus processes in heuristic evaluations to ensure that**
 - **Synchronous or more structured asynchronous consensus sessions help streamline rating discussions and improve alignment.**
 - **Better preparation of severity rating discussions ensures clearer prioritisation of usability problems.**

Even when preparing and conducting usability studies, unexpected participant

58

challenges can arise - especially in large-scale remote testing. UCQ-FRAME should emphasise structured pre-testing not only of tools, but also of participant experience, response accuracy and task usability, to ensure that full studies run smoothly and produce reliable findings. By embedding stronger pre-testing, consensus building, and cognitive load management into usability workflows, future studies can optimise participant engagement while maintaining high methodological rigour.

6.7 **Lack of a centralised repository for user research insights**

One of the main challenges encountered in evaluating GoTriple and building on previous research efforts was the lack of a dedicated **user research repository**, or a shared instance (e.g., Notion, Google Drive, Bryeta.ai), where (all) previous user related research could be (easily) accessed.

Currently, researchers rely on publicly distributed data, such as

- Zenodo-hosted materials, including user interviews from the initial planning, design and development phases of the TRIPLE project (De Paoli & Forbes, 2024).
- Published journal articles, conference proceedings and project deliverables that contain important user insights but are not centralised (Dumouchel et al., 2020).
- Complementary research, such as the results of the Atrium Researchers Forum, which are also available in Zenodo, but not in an easily searchable way (Delmazo & Umerle, 2024)

Without a structured, centralised repository of research insights, research efforts become fragmented and difficult to access, leading to

- Repetitive research efforts - teams inadvertently redo studies that have already been conducted.
- Stakeholders relying on individual researchers to surface past findings rather than being able to self-serve insights.
- Decision-making without a complete picture, as existing knowledge remains scattered and under-utilised.

On the other hand, a common problem in research operations - many attempts to build research repositories fail because they focus on storage rather than accessibility and actionability. As ResearchOps frameworks emphasise, the key to an effective research repository is not just how insights are stored, but how they surface at the right time and in the right context to inform decision-making (Pehar & Pavlović, 2023, p. 40).

Evidence from HE, MUT and URUT:

- URUT could have been better informed if previous usability studies on GoTriple were consolidated and easily accessible, ensuring that known pain points were not rediscovered in separate projects.
- Research findings were stored but not systematically reused, meaning that despite previous research, some usability evaluations had to start from scratch rather than building on previous findings.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

Promote a centralised, structured repository where research related to specific OPERAS services, such as GoTriple, is stored:

- Easily accessible to researchers, designers and decision makers.
- Continuously updated to reflect new findings and avoid duplication of research.
- Integrated with ongoing usability evaluation efforts to inform future UCQ-FRAME evaluations.

Ensure that research findings are not just stored, but brought to the surface when needed, in line with ResearchOps principles:

- Make insights visible in decision-making workflows - not buried in an archive.
- Link past research to current investigations, creating a continuous learning loop.
- Improve knowledge sharing culture, reducing reliance on individual researchers as "insight gatekeepers".
- Explore lightweight, scalable repository solutions (for example, Notion, a structured Google Drive instance, or a dedicated low-budget AI-powered repository such as [Bryeta.ai](#)) before committing to large-scale knowledge management tools.

Building a central repository alone is not the answer - it is how research is accessed and used that matters. **UCQ-FRAME should emphasise the visibility, accessibility and actionability of research, ensuring that past research is used to inform future evaluations.** By embedding structured knowledge management into usability research workflows, GoTriple and other OPERAS services can eliminate redundant effort and accelerate evidence-based improvements.

6.8 Post-fix usability validation: Ensuring the real impact of implemented changes

A challenge in usability evaluation is that fixing identified problems does not automatically result in an improved user experience. While usability testing can identify problems and suggest solutions, the actual impact of these fixes is rarely evaluated in a structured way.

A key question for UCQ-FRAME is: **How can we ensure that the usability improvements implemented improve the overall experience?** This requires:

- Post-fix usability testing to validate that changes improve task success and reduce friction.
- Tracking UX metrics (e.g. SUS, UEQ-S, NPS) before and after fixes to see if users perceive improvements.
- Ensure that developers and UX researchers are aligned, closing the loop between usability research and platform iteration.

Lessons from HE, MUT and URUT: The need for post-fix assessment

- HE provided structured usability recommendations, but there was no structured follow-up to confirm whether the fixes resolved user frustration.
- MUT captured real user challenges, but there was no systematic post-test validation of implemented changes.
- URUT's quantitative UX scores could be used as a benchmark, but no systematic comparison was made between pre-fix and post-fix usability ratings.

UCQ-FRAME refinements:

- **Recommend structured post-fix usability testing to ensure that implemented solutions are tested in follow-up studies.**
- **Track usability & UX scores (e.g. SUS, UEQ-S, NPS) before and after fixes to measure real impact on user perception.**
- **Ensure that usability researchers and developers have a continuous feedback loop that allows for refinement beyond the initial implementation.**

UCQ-FRAME should evolve to not only identify and document problems but also track whether fixes translate into meaningful improvements. Embedding post-fix usability validation will help ensure that platform improvements are user-driven, not just problem-solving driven.

6.9 Improving UCQ-FRAME for sustainable usability and UX evaluation

The GoTriple usability evaluation provided important insights for refining UCQ-FRAME as a structured framework for assessing user-centred quality in SSH research platforms. The triangulated approach - HE, MUT and URUT - revealed the strengths and limitations of different methods and highlighted areas for improvement. Key challenges, including participant recruitment, technological barriers to remote testing and the lack of a centralised research repository, highlighted the need for a more structured, scalable and sustainable approach to usability and UX evaluation.

To ensure long-term impact, UCQ-FRAME should promote iterative usability and UX evaluation, structured recruitment strategies and post-fix validation, ensuring that both task performance and user perception metrics are effectively integrated and tracked. In addition, the evaluation highlighted the importance of democratising the research process by involving users earlier in the development of the platform and incorporating their insights into usability assessments beyond the traditional testing phases. Strengthening user involvement will not only improve usability outcomes, but will also

promote greater alignment between researcher workflows, platform functionality and real-world needs.

By embedding usability and UX as ongoing processes rather than one-off evaluations, SSH platforms can evolve in line with researchers' needs. Future refinements of UCQ-FRAME should prioritise adaptability, efficiency, accessibility and participatory design, ensuring that usability and UX assessments remain actionable, scalable and embedded in platform development.

7 Conclusion and next steps

This chapter revisits the key RQs, summarises the most critical usability problems, assesses how effectively GoTriple supports users in performing research tasks, compares the findings from different evaluation methods, and identifies how these findings contribute to refining both the design of GoTriple and the UCQ-FRAME methodology.

Looking forward, the next steps will focus on further research and iterative improvements, including mobile usability enhancements, advanced feature testing, longitudinal user engagement studies, and benchmarking UX improvements over time. By integrating these findings into a sustainable usability strategy, GoTriple can continue to evolve as a research-centric discovery platform, ensuring long-term usability and user satisfaction.

7.1 Evaluating key findings through the research questions

This section analyses the RQs in detail, summarising key usability and UX findings and assessing how well GoTriple supports user workflows. It compares findings from HE, MUT and URUT, highlighting where the methods converge and diverge. Finally, it examines how these findings help to refine both the design of GoTriple and the UCQ-FRAME methodology, ensuring a structured approach to iterative usability improvement.

7.1.1 Key usability problems affecting GoTriple

RQ1: What are the key usability problems affecting the GoTriple platform?

The evaluation identified several serious usability challenges in key areas of GoTriple's interface and functionality, affecting navigation, search, filtering, multilingual support and bibliographic records.

- **Navigation and home page clarity:** Users struggled to understand the platform's mission and target audience, as the definition was placed at the bottom of the homepage, making it difficult to grasp the intended purpose upon entry.
- **Authentication and account management:** The registration and login/logout processes were confusing, particularly around the OPERAS ID, unclear

registration options, and a lack of flexibility in confirming authorship - forcing users into a single choice with no way to accurately indicate their status.

- Search and filtering issues: Including severe limitations on search functionality; inability to search across multiple fields such as title or abstract.
- Poor handling of special characters and diacritics, resulting in irrelevant search results.
- **Filtering:** Confusion between "recent" vs. "publication date" and "text" vs. "article", making content refinement inefficient.
- **Shortcomings in multilingual support:** The Croatian language interface had translation problems and inconsistencies that affected search performance and interface usability for non-English users.
- **Bibliographic records and citation/reference management:** Users were faced with incomplete metadata records, missing critical elements such as titles, page numbers, licences, DOI and affiliations. In addition, there was no support for downloading records in common citation styles (APA, Harvard, etc.).

👉 These findings confirm that GoTriple faces significant usability challenges, particularly around core platform navigation, search effectiveness and multilingual functionality, which need to be addressed to improve the user experience.

7.1.2 Effectiveness of GoTriple in supporting common tasks

RQ2: How effective does GoTriple support users in performing common tasks (e.g. finding a publication, discovering a dataset)?

The usability evaluation assessed how well GoTriple enables users to perform research-related tasks such as finding publications and datasets, refining search results, and evaluating bibliographic records.

- **Basic search:** While users appreciated the simplicity of the search interface, they struggled with query structuring, in particular due to
 - Lack of field-specific searches (e.g. title, abstract, keyword filters).
 - Manual entry of Boolean operators rather than selectable options.
 - Limited search guidance (no tutorials or query building assistance).
- **Filtering and refinement:** The platform's filtering system confused users, particularly with regard to
 - Vague filter labels (e.g. distinguishing between different types of content).
 - Undefined metadata categories, which made it difficult to refine search results.
- **Bibliographic information management:** The lack of structured metadata and citation export options made it difficult for researchers to
 - Review publication details efficiently.
 - Download citation-ready references for integration into their research workflow.
- **Multilingual search performance:** Search effectiveness was significantly reduced in Croatian, with unclear search labels, incomplete abstracts and

inconsistent results across languages.

👉 These results suggest that while GoTriple supports basic research tasks, usability limitations in searching, filtering and bibliographic data management hinder its effectiveness for researchers.

7.1.3 Comparison of evaluation methods: HE, MUT and URUT

RQ3: How do different evaluation methods (HE, MUT and URUT) compare in uncovering usability problems on GoTriple?

The study showed that HE, MUT and URUT work in a complementary way, with each method uncovering unique aspects of usability problems while reinforcing the findings of the other approaches.

HE:

- Most effective in the early stages of the evaluation, identifying structural usability problems such as navigation inconsistencies, unclear system feedback and search filtering issues.
- Did not capture real-world user problems as its findings were based on expert judgement rather than direct user interaction.

MUT:

- Provided in-depth qualitative insights, revealing cognitive overload, multilingual challenges and frustration with metadata completeness.
- Allowed for real-time exploration of user difficulties, making it the best method for understanding why users struggled with specific tasks.

URUT:

- Strengthened evaluation through large-scale validation, capturing UX perception metrics (UEQ-S, SUS, NPS) alongside task performance data.
- Uncovered technical and participant barriers, particularly in mobile usability and participant reluctance to install browser extensions for screen/audio sharing.

A triangulated approach combining expert review, real-time observation and large-scale validation provides the most complete picture of usability challenges and UX performance.

👉 These findings confirm that no single method is sufficient - HE, MUT and URUT together provide a complete picture of usability challenges, each contributing different but essential insights. A triangulated approach - combining expert review, real-time observation and large-scale validation - ensures that usability and UX issues are thoroughly assessed, increasing the reliability and completeness of the findings.

7.1.4 Refine GoTriple and UCQ-FRAME based on the results (RQ4).

RQ4: How can the findings from this evaluation be used to refine both the design

64

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of GoTriple and the UCQ-FRAME methodology itself?

The results of this evaluation provide clear recommendations for improving both GoTriple and UCQ-FRAME.

Refinements to GoTriple's design:

- Improve the clarity of the homepage to ensure that users immediately understand the purpose of the platform.
- Improve search functionality with field-specific search options, better handling of diacritics, and support for structured query building.
- Implement clearer filter labelling and metadata standardisation to improve the relevance of search results.
- Enhance multilingual usability with better translations and improved search consistency across languages.
- Enhance bibliographic data completeness and introduce citation export options in standard formats.

Refinements to the UCQ-FRAME methodology:

- Encourage earlier user involvement in usability evaluation and design refinement to ensure a democratised approach.
- Strengthen guidelines for managing participant recruitment, possibly exploring sustainable research panels to streamline the process.
- Improve post-fix validation practices to ensure that usability fixes are measured, iterated and re-evaluated over time.
- Formalise multi-method usability evaluation, ensuring that HE, MUT and URUT are integrated into iterative testing cycles rather than used in isolation.

👉 These findings reinforce the need for iterative usability improvements in the design of GoTriple, while refining UCQ-FRAME to ensure structured, user-centred evaluations that meet SSH research needs.

7.2 Next steps and areas for further research

The GoTriple usability evaluation provided a strong foundation for platform improvements, but as with any evaluation, there are areas that require further research, refinement, and validation. While the results of HE, MUT and URUT identified critical usability and UX challenges, some aspects - such as mobile usability, advanced features and longitudinal user engagement - require additional investigation. In addition, discrepancies between expert evaluations and real user feedback suggest the need for continued usability monitoring and iterative design improvements.

Moving forward, next steps should focus on prioritising immediate usability improvements, expanding research efforts to cover underexplored areas, and ensuring an iterative process for refining both GoTriple and the UCQ-FRAME methodology.

7.2.1 Improving mobile and responsive usability

The evaluation focused primarily on GoTriple's desktop experience, but URUT revealed

low mobile participation, suggesting that mobile usability remains under-tested and potentially problematic. With many researchers conducting searches on mobile devices, ensuring full mobile optimisation is critical.

Key areas for further research:

- **Mobile navigation and filtering usability** - Do issues identified with desktop filtering (e.g. visibility of options) persist or worsen on mobile?
- **Touch-based interactions and UI responsiveness** - Are buttons, scroll areas and selection options optimised for mobile touch interactions?
- **Consistency of usability across devices** - How well does the mobile version maintain functionality compared to the desktop version?

Future usability testing should explicitly include mobile users, focusing on responsive design, touch interaction efficiency and cross-platform consistency to ensure a seamless experience across devices.

7.2.2 Evaluation of advanced features (Knowledge Map, Streamgraph, AI Chatbot)

The current evaluation primarily assessed core usability features, but GoTriple is expanding its capabilities with advanced discovery tools such as the Knowledge Map, Streamgraph, and an AI chatbot (as discussed in the Atrium Researcher Forum report: Delmazo & Umerle, 2024). These tools introduce new user interactions that require dedicated usability testing.

Future research should:

- Assess how users engage with these advanced features - Are they intuitive and do they improve research discovery?
- Ensure seamless integration with core search workflows - Do these features complement or conflict with existing search behaviours?
- Assess onboarding needs - Do users need guidance to use these features effectively?

By incorporating usability testing for advanced features early in the development process, GoTriple can ensure that these innovations enhance rather than hinder the user experience.

7.2.3 Assessing long-term user engagement and content relevance

The evaluation focused on short-term usability interactions, but understanding how researchers use GoTriple over time is crucial to refining strategies for user retention, engagement and satisfaction. A longitudinal study could reveal:

- Do usability challenges persist after repeated use, or do users adapt?

- How does perceived usefulness change over time?
- Do users consistently find relevant content, or do they experience search fatigue while trying to reach relevant results?

Possible research methods include

- Multi-session user studies - tracking the same users over several weeks to observe changes in behaviour.
- Qualitative follow-ups - interviewing users after long-term use to identify ongoing pain points or areas for improvement.

Understanding long-term user engagement helps prioritise persistent issues and refine features to ensure continued usability and relevance.

7.2.4 Continuous benchmarking and iterative UX improvements

Benchmarking against similar academic search platforms was initially undertaken during the planning phase of the TRIPLE project, providing a comparative analysis of usability, feature sets and UX design (Dumouchel et al., 2020). However, benchmarking should be an ongoing process to ensure that GoTriple evolves in line with best practice and user expectations.

Future benchmarking efforts should

- Compare GoTriple's UX performance (e.g. search efficiency, filtering, and discoverability) with similar platforms.
- Track usability and UX metrics over time, integrating SUS, UEQ-S and NPS scores for iterative improvement.
- Use post-implementation usability testing to verify that previous usability challenges have been successfully resolved.

By embedding continuous benchmarking and UX monitoring into the GoTriple development cycle, the platform can ensure sustainable usability improvements and long-term user engagement.

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Appendices

The appendices provide supporting material and evidence for the evaluation process described in the report. They serve as a source of transparency, allowing others to see how the study was conducted and to review the detailed findings and data that support the report's conclusions and recommendations. Any sensitive information has been removed or anonymised in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Appendix A - Heuristic review checklist

This appendix contains the checklist used by the evaluators during the heuristic evaluation, based on Nielsen's ten heuristics.

Usability Evaluation of the GoTriple Desktop Platform Using Nielsen's Heuristics

Objective

The objective of this exercise is to conduct a heuristic evaluation of the GoTriple platform, utilizing Jakob Nielsen's ten usability heuristics. This initial assessment aims to identify usability problems and deviations from established usability principles. By highlighting these issues, we can address them before proceeding to more detailed user testing.

Purpose

The heuristic evaluation will serve as the first step in our comprehensive usability assessment process. This evaluation will help us uncover usability problems that may affect the user experience, providing a foundation for improvements. The findings will be used to enhance the platform's usability before moving on to un-moderated user testing.

- [Heuristic evaluation workshop presentation with detailed instructions](#) (for internal use only)

Heuristic Evaluation Overview

- Evaluators: A team of usability or subject experts will perform the evaluation independently.
- Focus: Evaluators will assess the GoTriple platform based on Jakob Nielsen's ten usability heuristics, focusing on identifying any deviations from these principles.
- Method: Each evaluator will individually review the platform, documenting instances where the platform does not conform to the heuristic principles."

Areas to be Evaluated

Area	Description
Homepage Navigation (HomeNav)	Evaluate clarity and ease of navigating the homepage, including menu items, links, and layout.

User Registration (Sign Up)	Assess the user registration process for ease of use, clarity of instructions, and form field appropriateness.
Log In and Out (Login / Logout)	Examine the login and logout processes for clarity and feedback on user actions.
Searching for Information (Search)	Review search functionality for effectiveness, including options, results accuracy, and ease of use.

Heuristic Name	Description	Examples	Poster
H1 - Visibility of system status	The system should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	No loading indicators during data retrieval processes - No confirmation message after a form submission - No feedback on active navigation state	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_1_compressed.pdf
H2 - Match between system and the real world	The system should speak the users' language, with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user, rather than system-oriented terms.	Using technical jargon instead of user-friendly terms - Misleading labels that do not match the content they represent - Confusing system messages	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_2_compressed.pdf
H3 - User control and freedom	Users often choose system functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue.	No "Back" button or option to undo actions - No cancel button during processes like form submission - Lack of exit options during multi-step processes	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_3_compressed.pdf
H4 - Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing. Follow platform conventions.	Inconsistent terminology for similar actions - Different icon designs for similar	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_4_compressed.pdf

		functions - Inconsistent layout and navigation structures	
H5 - Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design that prevents a problem from occurring in the first place.	No validation for input fields, allowing erroneous data submission - No preventive measures against common user errors - No guidance on mandatory fields	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_5_compressed.pdf
H6 - Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the dialogue to another.	No breadcrumb trails to indicate the user's location - Hidden or hard-to-find controls and options - Lack of visible labels and instructions	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/Heuristic_6_compressed.pdf
H7 - Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the system can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users.	No keyboard shortcuts or quick access options - No advanced search or navigation features for experienced users - Lack of customization options	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/NNq_Jakob's_Usability_Heuristic_7.pdf
H8 - Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	Cluttered interfaces with too much information - Unnecessary graphics or text that distracts from primary tasks - Overly complex navigation menus	https://www.nngroup.com/articles/aesthetic-minimalist-design/
H9 - Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	Vague or confusing error messages - Error messages without guidance on how to fix the problem - Use of	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/NNq_Jakob's_Usability_Heuristic_9.pdf

from errors		error codes instead of plain language	
H10 - Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	No accessible help or documentation links - Help content that is hard to search or navigate - Overly complex or too brief documentation without useful details	https://media.nngroup.com/media/articles/attachments/NNq_Jakob's_Usability_Heuristics_10.pdf

Severity Rating

0 - No problems found (serves just as a reminder that the principle has been checked).

1 - Minor usability problems (cosmetic issues that do not significantly impact usability).

2 - Moderate usability problems (issues that affect usability but do not severely hinder task completion).

3 - Severe usability problems (critical issues that severely impact usability and task completion).

Documentation

Findings Specify instances of non-conformity with each heuristic. Provide detailed descriptions of the issues you encounter. If there are multiple findings related to the same affected area and heuristic, add a new row for each finding to ensure clarity and thoroughness.

Notes and suggestions Provide actionable suggestions for improvement alongside the identified issues. Highlight potential solutions or design changes that could address the usability problems you've noted.

Screenshots Upload individual or grouped screenshots for each affected area and heuristic. Name each screenshot using the format: [EvaluatorInitials][Area][HeuristicNumber]_[Description] (e.g., FP_HomeNav_H1_NoFeedback.png). See column "I" for naming suggestions.

Checklist for the heuristic evaluation

Heuristic & Issues	Brief Description
H1 - Visibility of System Status	
NoFeedback	No feedback is provided when an action is performed.
SlowResponse	System takes too long to respond to user actions.
UnclearProgress	Progress indicators are unclear, misleading, or absent.
HiddenStatus	Status messages or notifications are hidden or not prominently visible.
ErrorNotified	Errors, warnings, or issues are not communicated to the user.
StatusOverload	Too many status updates overwhelm the user.
InconsistentStatus	Status information varies or is inconsistent across the platform.
MisleadingStatus	Status information is misleading or incorrect.
DelayedFeedback	Feedback on actions is provided too late.
ConfusingIndicators	Indicators are unclear or confusing.
OverlyTechnicalStatus	Status messages use overly technical language.
StatusErrors	Errors in status updates or progress indicators.
NoSystemMessages	System messages that are important for understanding the state are missing.
HomepageStatus	Status information on the homepage is not up-to-date or unclear.
HiddenErrors	Errors related to sign-up, log-in, or search are not visible to users.
InadequateSearchFeedback	Feedback during search operations is unclear or missing.
UnclearLoading	Loading indicators during search or navigation are absent or unclear.
H2 - Match Between System and the Real World	
ConfusingTerms	Use of jargon, technical terms, or abbreviations unfamiliar to users.
NonStandardIcons	Icons or symbols that are not recognizable or intuitive.
InconsistentMetaphors	Metaphors used do not align with users' real-world

	experiences.
OutOfOrderContent	Content is presented in a confusing or non-intuitive order.
UnfamiliarControls	Controls or elements do not align with users' real-world expectations.
MisleadingLabels	Labels that misrepresent their functions or do not match users' expectations.
CulturalMismatch	Content or design that does not align with users' cultural contexts or expectations.
InappropriateMetaphors	Metaphors used are irrelevant or inappropriate for the context.
NonIntuitiveNavigation	Navigation elements are not intuitive or familiar.
UnfamiliarActions	Actions or features are not consistent with real-world expectations.
ConfusingGrouping	Related items are not grouped logically or intuitively.
IncongruentDesign	Design elements do not match the context or user expectations.
AmbiguousIcons	Icons do not clearly represent their intended actions or functions.
NonStandardLinks	Links in the footer or homepage do not follow standard web conventions.
MisplacedSearchField	Search field placement or function is inconsistent with user expectations.
UnclearSignUp/Login	Sign-up and login processes use terms or steps that are confusing or unfamiliar.
MisalignedFilterOptions	Filtering options do not align with user expectations or real-world usage.
H3 - User Control and Freedom	
LackUndo	No option to undo or redo actions.
ForcedActions	Users are forced into a specific workflow without flexibility.
NoExit	No clear way to exit or cancel an operation.
HiddenNavigation	Navigation options are not easily discoverable.
RestrictedFreedom	Restrictions on user freedom that impede task completion.

NoCustomActions	Users cannot customize or personalize their actions or preferences.
IrreversibleActions	Critical actions cannot be undone or modified.
InflexibleInteractions	Interaction methods are rigid and do not allow for user preferences.
OverlyPrescriptive	System imposes strict procedures without allowing user discretion.
NoAbortOption	No option to abort or cancel ongoing operations.
HiddenOptions	Some options are hidden and not readily accessible.
LackRetry	No option to retry failed actions.
InconsistentControls	Controls for undoing or repeating actions are inconsistent.
NoEasyLogout	Logout option is not easily accessible or intuitive.
RestrictedSearch	Search functionalities are too restrictive and do not allow for flexibility.
UnclearSignUp/LogOut	Sign-up and log-out processes lack clear user control or freedom.
OvercomplicatedSearch	Search functionalities are too complex or restrictive.
H4 - Consistency and Standards	
InconsistentDesign	Design elements, such as colors and fonts, vary across pages or sections.
MixedTerminology	Different terms are used for the same concept or function.
VariableLayouts	Layouts change unexpectedly between pages or sections.
NonStandardBehavior	Elements behave in unexpected or non-standard ways.
ConfusingLabels	Labels, instructions, or terminology are inconsistent or unclear.
UnpredictableResults	Actions produce results that are inconsistent or unexpected.
DiscrepantFunctionality	Functionality varies across similar elements or sections.
InconsistentColorSchemes	Color schemes differ between pages or sections inappropriately.
NonUniformDesign	Design elements are not uniform across the platform.
ConflictingActions	Actions or elements have conflicting purposes or functions.

IrregularNavigation	Navigation elements function differently across pages or sections.
InconsistentInteraction	Interaction methods vary in a way that confuses users.
VariableSearchResults	Search results presentation varies unexpectedly.
InconsistentFooterLinks	Footer links behave inconsistently or are not uniform across pages.
UnpredictableSignUp/Login	Sign-up and login forms have inconsistent behavior or styling.
VariableHelpResources	Help resources or tooltips vary unpredictably across the site.
H5 - Error Prevention	
UnclearInstructions	Instructions or error messages are vague or not helpful.
MissingValidation	Lack of input validation to prevent errors before submission.
UnhelpfulErrorMessage	Error messages do not provide adequate guidance for resolving issues.
InconsistentValidation	Validation rules are applied inconsistently or are unclear.
AbsenceOfConfirmation	Lack of confirmation for critical actions or decisions.
OverlookedErrors	Errors that are not highlighted or addressed before final submission.
ImproperDefaults	Default settings or values that lead to common user errors.
ConfusingErrorMessage	Error messages are unclear or ambiguous.
MissingErrorFeedback	Feedback on errors is missing or inadequate.
UnclearErrorResolution	Error messages do not provide specific guidance for resolution.
InadequateValidation	Validation checks are insufficient or poorly implemented.
InconsistentErrorHandling	Error handling processes vary across the platform.
IneffectiveWarnings	Warnings are ineffective or do not prevent errors.
MissingSearchValidation	Search input validation is missing or unclear.
InadequateSignUp/Login Validation	Sign-up and login forms lack sufficient validation or error feedback.

UnclearFilterErrors	Errors or issues with filters or facets are not clearly communicated.
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H6 - Recognition Rather Than Recall

HiddenOptions	Options or features are not readily visible and require memorization.
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LackHelp	No help or guidance is provided when needed.
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InadequateLabels	Labels or instructions are not descriptive enough to aid recognition.
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UnclearIcons	Icons do not clearly represent their functions or are ambiguous.
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MissingHints	No hints or cues to help users remember how to use features.
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NonPredictiveDesign	Design elements do not follow expected patterns or conventions.
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LackOfFeedback	Absence of feedback for actions that require user recognition.
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UnavailableHelp	Help resources are not available when needed.
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HiddenFeatures	Features are not easily discoverable and require recall.
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PoorlyDesignedHelp	Help resources are poorly designed or not user-friendly.
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UnhelpfulTooltips	Tooltips do not provide useful information or aid recognition.
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ComplexNavigation	Navigation requires users to remember complex sequences.
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InadequateSearchHelp	Search field lacks adequate help or hints for effective use.
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PoorSignUp/Login Guidance	Sign-up and login processes do not provide adequate guidance or cues.
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HiddenFilterOptions	Filter options are not readily visible or discoverable.
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InconsistentHelp	Help or tips are inconsistent across different areas of the platform.
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H7 - Flexibility and Efficiency of Use

InflexibleProcesses	Processes are rigid with no options for shortcuts or customization.
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OvercomplicatedTasks	Tasks are unnecessarily complex or involve too many steps.
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NoShortcuts	Lack of keyboard shortcuts or quick actions for advanced users.
PoorEfficiency	Inefficient workflows that slow down task completion.
LimitedCustomizability	Limited options for users to customize their experience.
RepetitiveTasks	Users must perform repetitive tasks without the option for automation.
CumbersomeNavigation	Navigation or task flows that require excessive effort or time.
InefficientDesign	Design elements that hinder efficient task completion.
LackAdaptiveOptions	No options for adapting processes to user preferences or needs.
InadequateAutomation	Automation options are limited or absent.
SlowProcesses	Processes or interactions are slower than necessary.
UnpredictableShortcuts	Shortcuts produce unexpected results or are inconsistent.
ComplexFilterOptions	Filtering options are overly complex or restrictive.
InefficientSearchResults	Search results presentation is inefficient or cumbersome.
RigidSignUp/Login	Sign-up and login processes are inflexible and do not accommodate user needs.
LimitedSearchCustomization	Limited options to customize search queries or filters.

H8 - Aesthetic and Minimalist Design

ClutteredInterface	Interface is overloaded with unnecessary elements or information.
DistractingDesign	Design elements that distract from the main content or purpose.
OveruseOfColors	Excessive or inappropriate use of colors that complicates understanding.
InconsistentTypography	Inconsistent or distracting use of fonts and typography.
UnnecessaryDetails	Inclusion of irrelevant or superfluous details that do not add value.
VisualNoise	Excessive visual elements that contribute to cognitive overload.
PoorAlignment	Content or elements are poorly aligned, affecting

	readability.
InappropriateDesign	Design elements are not appropriate for the context or content.
ExcessiveText	Text is overly verbose or not concise.
UnrelatedGraphics	Graphics that do not support or enhance the content.
ClutteredLayout	Layout is crowded and difficult to navigate.
DistractingAnimations	Animations that detract from the user experience or task completion.
OverwhelmingTips	Tips or guidance on the homepage are overwhelming or intrusive.
ExcessiveSearchFields	Search fields or options are overly complicated or cluttered.
DisorganizedFooter	Footer elements are disorganized or cluttered.
InconsistentVisuals	Visual elements vary inconsistently across the platform.
H9 - Help Users Recognize, Diagnose, and Recover from Errors	
UnclearErrorResolution	Error messages lack specific guidance for resolving issues.
LackRecoveryOptions	No options provided for users to recover from errors or mistakes.
GenericErrorMessage	Error messages are too generic and do not assist in diagnosing the problem.
NoErrorFeedback	Feedback on errors is missing or inadequate.
ComplexErrorRecovery	Recovery steps are complex and not user-friendly.
InadequateHelp	Help resources do not address error recovery effectively.
DelayedFeedback	Feedback on errors is provided too late for effective resolution.
IneffectiveErrorMessages	Error messages do not effectively guide users in resolving issues.
UnclearRecoverySteps	Steps to recover from errors are unclear or confusing.
LackPreventiveMeasures	No measures in place to prevent errors from occurring.
ConfusingRecoveryOptions	Recovery options are unclear or not easy to follow.
InaccessibleErrorHelp	Help for error recovery is not easily accessible or discoverable.

NoSearchErrorHandling	Search errors are not handled effectively or communicated clearly.
ComplexSignUp/Login Errors	Errors during sign-up and login are complex and difficult to resolve.
InadequateFilteringError Handling	Errors related to filtering options are not handled well.
UnclearResultsErrorHandling	Issues with search results or visualizations are not clearly addressed.
H10 - Help and Documentation	
InaccessibleHelp	Help or documentation is not easily accessible or discoverable.
UnhelpfulDocumentation	Documentation is not useful or does not address common issues.
LackExamples	Absence of examples or use cases in help resources.
OutdatedInformation	Documentation contains outdated or incorrect information.
NoSearchFunction	Lack of search functionality within help resources.
PoorHelpOrganization	Help resources are poorly organized or difficult to navigate.
InadequateSearchTips	Tips provided during search operations are inadequate or unclear.
MissingSignUp/Login Help	Help resources for sign-up and login processes are missing or inadequate.
IncompleteDocumentation	Documentation does not cover all features or common issues.
UnclearHelpGuidance	Help or documentation is not clear or straightforward.
NonComprehensiveHelp	Help resources are not comprehensive enough for troubleshooting.
IneffectiveSearchHelp	Search help is not effective or does not guide users well.
IncompleteErrorHelp	Documentation does not adequately cover error handling or recovery.

Example of an expert evaluator's heuristic evaluation checklist

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Evaluator	Affected Area / Related Tasks	Choose Heuristic Violated	Severity Rating	Findings (Description)	Notes and Suggestions	FindingShortName	Upload Screenshots	Screenshot
2	FP	HomeNav	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate pr...	The user chooses the "Disciplines" option fro Optimise content or structure; Improv	SlowResponse	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
3	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	3 - Severe prob...	This issue occurs under the Membership sect Separate issues reporting from Memnt	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
4	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	3 - Severe prob...	The phrase "Search Resources and Users" a Make explicit what "Resources" refer	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
5	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	The term "Profiles" in the GoTriple numbers s Provide more context around what "P	MisleadingLabels	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
6	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	The term "Most Popular" is generic and lacks Clarify the basis of popularity; Addres	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
7	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	The term "Documents" is broad and may con Add a brief description below the num	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
8	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	Users may expect that all links in the footer (" Use visual cues, such as an icon (e.g	NonStandardLinks	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
9	FP	HomeNav	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	1 - Minor probl...	When users search without entering any term Instead of using "valid search term", s	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
10	FP	HomeNav	H3: User Control and Freedom	2 - Moderate pr...	The user is unable to proceed or use the plat Fix the link to the Homepage. The bu	RestrictedFreedom	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
11	FP	HomeNav	H3: User Control and Freedom	3 - Severe prob...	No feedback for consent actions. Users expe After clicking "Reject all" or "Accept a	RestrictedFreedom	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
12	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor probl...	The top color of the overlay message is black Update the overlay to match the color	InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
13	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor probl...	The language of the lubenda message might. Reword the overlay text to make it mc	ConfusingLabels	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
14	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	1 - Minor probl...	The lubenda icon, presented in the bottom rig Consider adding a label next to the lu	InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
15	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate pr...	The inconsistent color scheme between the c Ensure that the consent panel follows	InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
16	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate pr...	Inconsistency in terms usage like "Users," "A Choose one term (e.g., "Authors") and	MixedTerminology	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
17	FP	HomeNav	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate pr...	Inconsistency in terms usage like "Resources Choose one term (e.g., "Publications")	MixedTerminology	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
18	FP	HomeNav	H5: Error Prevention	0 - no problem			Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
19	FP	HomeNav	H6: Recognition Rather than Recall	2 - Moderate pr...	The recommendations in the "Tailored For Yo Provide users with a brief introduction	HiddenFeatures	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
20	FP	HomeNav	H6: Recognition Rather than Recall	3 - Severe prob...	The feature to find collaborators is not easily Add a dedicated section or link on the	HiddenFeatures	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
21	FP	HomeNav	H7: Flexibility and Efficiency of Use	3 - Severe prob...	The current search functionality caters only ic Include a link or button next to the se	LimitedSearchCus...	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
22	FP	HomeNav	H8: Aesthetic and Minimalist Design	1 - Minor probl...	The inconsistent color scheme between the c Ensure that the consent panel follows	InappropriateDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
23	FP	HomeNav	H9: Help Users Recognize, Diagnose, and	3 - Severe prob...	When users enter one or two characters (e.g Improve the error message by explic	ClearErrorMessages	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
24	FP	HomeNav	H10: Help and Documentation	2 - Moderate pr...	Relying on an external platform like Zenodo f Implement a dedicated documentation	AccessibleHelp	Upload Screenshots	FP_HomeNav	
25	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate pr...	The Sign Up page requires users to accept to Allow users with an existing account t	ConfusingIndicators	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
26	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate pr...	The three-step progress indicator is not anym Ensure that the three-step progress i	UnclearProgress	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
27	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	3 - Severe prob...	The error message "An error occurred when The error message should clearly cor	MisleadingStatus	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
28	FP	SignUp	H1: Visibility of System Status	2 - Moderate pr...	The Sign UP confirmation message indicates Include clear next steps (e.g., "Please	HiddenStatus	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
29	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	1 - Minor probl...	The term "Operas account" may not be famili Provide a short explanation of what a	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
30	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	When users enter one or two characters (e.g Improve the error message by explic	ConfusingTerms	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
31	FP	SignUp	H2: Match Between the System and the Re...	2 - Moderate pr...	The label "Go back to portal" in the sign up cc Clarify the label to explicitly state whe	NonInclusiveNaviga...	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
32	FP	SignUp	H3: User Control and Freedom	1 - Minor probl...	The inconsistency in wording between "Sign I Ensure that the language used throug	InconsistentControls	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
33	FP	SignUp	H3: User Control and Freedom	2 - Moderate pr...	The user is unable to easily return to the prev include a clear, visible "Back" or "Cha	ForcedActions	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	
34	FP	SignUp	H4: Consistency and Standards	2 - Moderate pr...	The Sign Up page fails to maintain a clear di For new users: "Follow these three st	InconsistentDesign	Upload Screenshots	FP_SignUp_H	

Appendix B - MUT script in English and consent form in Croatian

Contains the moderator's script for the moderated sessions - welcome script, task instructions and probing questions for each task. Also includes the task scenarios given to the participants.

Moderated Usability Testing Script (Moderator Version)

* Moderator instructions are highlighted in yellow or labeled as "[MODERATOR NOTE]" to indicate that they are not to be spoken aloud.

Participant	Online/Lab
Participant 1	UX Lab
Participant 2	UX Lab
Participant 3	Online, Google Meet
Participant 4	UX Lab
Participant 5	Online, Google Meet
Participant 6	Online, Google Meet

Opening the interview

Greeting research participants

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this usability testing session for the GoTriple platform. My name is Nikolina, and I will be facilitating today's session.

* *Yellow colors: for the moderator, no talking*

To begin, I will explain to you what this session will look like.

[What is being tested]

The purpose of this session is to evaluate the **GoTriple platform**. We are not evaluating your skills or ability to successfully complete the tasks. Your feedback will help us identify what works well within the platform and what can be improved. If you encounter any difficulties while using the system, it's likely that other users might face the same challenges. This is why your feedback is so important—it will allow us to address these issues and enhance the user experience for all future users of the GoTriple platform.

[Session Details]

During today's session, which will last approximately one hour, we will ask you to complete several **tasks** on the platform. Please interact with the system as you normally would and "**think out loud**" while performing the tasks. This means verbalizing your thoughts, such as what you are trying to achieve, what you expect to happen, or what you find confusing. We use this method to better understand your thought process and how you experience the platform.

Thinking out loud may feel unusual at first, but it is very helpful for our research. If you forget to think out loud at any point, don't worry—I will gently remind you.

[Honesty]

It is very important to be honest during this session. I was not involved in the development of this platform, so you don't need to worry about hurting my feelings. The purpose of this research is to identify any issues with the system or negative experiences you may have while interacting with it. Your honesty will help us make meaningful improvements to the platform.

[Explain what technology will be used]

Now I will explain how we will conduct the testing. You will access the GoTriple platform on your computer and use it as you would in a real-life scenario. We will record the session, including audio and screen activity, so that I can focus on observing and speaking with you. The recordings will **only be shared with my colleagues for research purposes**.

[Instructions during the session]

During the session, I will provide instructions, ask questions, and take notes, but I will not assist you if you get stuck. If you feel that you have completed a task or are unable to complete it, please let me know, and I will ask you a **few questions about your experience with that activity**.

- If you would like to take a break or move on to the next task, feel free to let me know at any time.

[Instruct the respondent to give informed consent to record the session]

As explained earlier, this session will be recorded to help researchers gain a better understanding of your interaction with the system and to identify any issues you may encounter while completing the tasks. The recordings will include audio and screen activity.

The collected recordings will be used solely for the purpose of analysing the results of this research and will never be linked to your personal information.

Please remember that you can withdraw from the research at any time.

To proceed, please review and sign the consent form (Attachment) to confirm your agreement.

Thank you. We can now begin the activities. Are you ready?

- Do you have any questions before the session begins?

[Turn on recording!]

Pre-test questionnaire

(Ask sub-questions without providing answers, max 5 minutes)

Demographics and Background:

- Can you tell me a bit about yourself? What is your current academic or professional role or position?
- What is your area of research or study?
- Besides Croatian, what languages do you use for reading, searching, or conducting activities related to your scientific research?

Computer and Digital Literacy:

How would you rate your computer literacy?

- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Advanced

Previous Experience Using the Platform:

How often do you use search platforms?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Periodically
- Rarely

[Sub-questions: What type of system do you use? For what purpose]

- For what purpose do you use search platforms?
- Can you tell me about your previous experience with literature search platforms

- or similar tools?
- How often do you use tools to search for research papers, such as Google Scholar or JSTOR?

[Transition:]

Now we will move on to the activities. Are you ready?

As I mentioned at the beginning, we are testing the platform, not your skills or your ability to successfully complete the activities. I want to remind you to **“think out loud”** as you work through the tasks so we can better understand your thought process and the flow you experience during the activities.

For **in-person participants**: Please put the interface **in full-screen** mode by clicking the icon in the upper right corner.

For online participants: Please also share your screen so we can observe your interaction with the platform.

Scenario 1

Imagine you are a researcher looking for a platform that could help you find academic resources for your work. You come across the GoTriple platform.

Task 1:

Take a few minutes to review the platform on the provided **link or screen**:

- a) What impression does it give you?
- b) What do you think the platform offers?

(Please do not click on anything yet.)

Moderator Note: Focus on understanding the participant's initial interpretation of the platform's purpose before moving to sub-questions. Encourage them to think out loud throughout this task.

Knowledge of the GoTriple Platform:

- Have you used the GoTriple platform before?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, how often do you use it?
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - Rarely

What features of the GoTriple platform have you used? (e.g., search, knowledge graph, export tools, etc.)

Scenario 2

Imagine you are writing a paper exploring the challenges posed by artificial intelligence in education within your academic field. Your task is to find relevant content on this topic using the GoTriple platform.

Task 2: Independent Literature Search

Instructions:

1. Before starting your search, take a moment to familiarize yourself with the homepage and the platform's available functionalities.
2. Think out loud while you research, as if you were alone in the room. Share your thoughts, observations, and any concerns that come to mind.
3. When you feel ready, use the GoTriple search engine as you would other search platforms you normally use (e.g., Google Scholar, ResearchGate).
4. Explore and use all available functionalities to help you find relevant sources.
5. If you encounter difficulties or have any questions, feel free to stop and ask me.

After Completing the Task – Discussion About the Experience:

- How easy or difficult was it for you to use the GoTriple search engine to find relevant content?
- Were there any features or aspects of the platform that you found particularly helpful during your search?
- Did you encounter anything that was confusing or slowed you down?
- Was it clear to you how to identify which works were available in full text?
- What would you suggest improving in the results display or the search options?

After Entering a Query and Viewing the Results:

- Please take a few moments to familiarize yourself with the search results page.

Sub-questions:

- Was the layout of the results page clear and easy to understand?
- Did anything surprise you, or did you notice anything missing in the results display?

After the Task is Completed: Metrics

Sub-question 1:

- What is your overall impression of this activity?

Sub-question 2:

- On a scale of 1-5 (1 – not at all satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied), how satisfied are you with this experience (task)?
- Why did you give that particular rating? Please explain.

Sub-question 3:

- Is there anything you particularly liked about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. (*Ask sub-questions to explore further.*)
 - E.g., Why do you find it clear or simple to use?

Sub-question 4:

- Is there anything you didn't like about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. (*Ask sub-questions to explore further.*)
 - E.g., Why do you find it unclear or difficult?

Sub-question 5:

- Do you have any suggestions to improve the experience of performing this task?

Transition to the Next Activity:

- Do you have any additional comments before we move on to the next activity?

Now, we will move on to the next activity.

[Moderator's Note:] Remind the respondent to think aloud during the next activity.

Scenario 3

Now that you have obtained search results on the challenges posed by artificial intelligence in the field of education, your task is to carefully assess the relevance of the presented papers.

Task 3: Assessing the Relevance of the Search Results Obtained

Instructions:

- Stay on the search results page for a while to familiarize yourself with the

86

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interface and the results displayed.

- Carefully review the results by examining the list of titles provided.
- Select 2–3 papers that you find most relevant to the topic you are researching.
- Think out loud as you analyze the results, sharing how you determine what is relevant and what is not.
- If you encounter any difficulties or have any questions, feel free to pause and ask me.

After Completing the Task – Discussion About the Experience:

- Did the titles and abstracts of the papers meet your expectations?
- How diverse and useful were the results for your topic?
- Did you notice any results that were thematically irrelevant or unexpected?
- What helped you the most in assessing which papers were useful for your research?
- What would you improve in how the results are displayed to make it easier to assess the relevance of the content?

(Encourage the participant to think out loud during the discussion.)

After Completing the Task – Metrics:

Sub-question 1:

- What is your overall impression of this activity?

Sub-question 2:

- On a scale of 1–5 (1 – not at all satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied), how satisfied are you with this experience (task)?
 - Why did you give that particular rating? Please explain.

Sub-question 3:

- Is there anything you particularly liked about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask follow-up questions to explore further.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it clear or simple?

Sub-question 4:

- Is there anything you didn't like about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask follow-up questions to explore further.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it unclear or difficult?

Sub-question 5:

- Do you have any suggestions to improve the experience of completing this task?

Transition to the Next Activity:

- Do you have any additional comments before we move on to the next activity?

Now, we will move on to the next activity.

Scenario 4

Imagine you are in the final stages of writing your research paper on the challenges posed by artificial intelligence in education. At this point, you need to find recent scientific articles published in the last five years that are available in open access. You also want to sort the results so that the most recent papers appear at the top for immediate use in your research.

Task 4: Using Filters to Narrow Results

Using the available filters on the GoTriple platform, narrow your search results based on the following criteria:

- Year of publication: Last 5 years (2020–2024)
- Content type: Scientific articles
- Availability: Open Access
- Sort by: Most recent

Instructions:

- Locate and apply the appropriate filters to narrow your results.
- Adjust the sorting to display the most recent works at the top of the results.
- Think aloud as you apply filters and sorting options, sharing your thoughts on their clarity, ease of use, and usefulness.
- If you encounter any difficulties or have questions, feel free to stop and ask me for clarification.

After Completing the Task – Discussion of the Experience:

- Were the filters clearly labelled and easily accessible?
- Were the filtering options (filter names and categories) understandable?

- If not, what was unclear?
- Did you easily find the option to sort results by the latest date?
- Did the filters and sorting options help you find more relevant and recent results?
 - If not, what additional filtering or sorting options would have been helpful?
- How would you rate the speed of updating results after applying filters and sorting?
- Are there any filtering or sorting options you typically use in other databases that were missing here?
- Is there anything you would improve in the display or functionality of the filters and sorting options?

(Encourage the participant to think aloud throughout the discussion.)

After Completing the Task – Metrics:

Sub-question 1:

- What is your overall impression of this task?

Sub-question 2:

- On a scale of 1–5 (1 – not at all satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied), how satisfied are you with this experience?
 - Why did you give that particular rating? Please explain.

Sub-question 3:

- Is there anything you particularly liked about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask follow-up questions as needed.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it clear or simple to use?

Sub-question 4:

- Is there anything you didn't like about this experience while performing this task?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask follow-up questions as needed.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it unclear or difficult?

Sub-question 5:

- Do you have any suggestions to improve the experience of completing this task?

Transition to the Next Task:

- Do you have any additional comments before we move on to the next task?

Now, we will move on to the next task.

[Moderator's Note:] Remind the participant to think aloud during the next task.

Scenario 5

Now that you have narrowed down your search results and identified potentially relevant papers, your task is to further verify the relevance of individual papers. Imagine that you want to include one of these papers in your research paper on the challenges posed by artificial intelligence in the field of education.

Task 5: Detailed Analysis and Download of the Bibliographic Record

Instructions:

- Select one paper from the search results that seems most relevant to you.
- Open the detailed view of the bibliographic data for the selected work and familiarize yourself with the information presented.
- Use the available details (e.g., title, abstract, authors, keywords, source) to determine whether the paper is truly relevant to your topic.
- If the paper is not relevant enough, return to the results page and repeat the analysis with another paper.
- If you determine the paper is relevant, download its bibliographic record using your preferred method.

! Note for the Moderator:

The bibliographic record can be downloaded through:

- Integrated export functions (e.g., BibTeX, JSON, JSON-LD).
 - Web clippers or extensions for tools like Zotero or Mendeley.
 - Standard copy-paste methods for users without reference management systems.
-

After Completing the Task – Discussion About the Experience:

- Was all the key bibliographic information clearly presented?

90

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- Was any important information missing (e.g., DOI, ISSN, type of paper)?
- How easy or difficult was it to assess the relevance of the paper based on the displayed information?
- Did you find the bibliographic data display clear and intuitive to use?
- How did you download the bibliographic record?
 - Are you familiar with the offered download formats (BibTeX, JSON, JSON-LD)?
 - Would you prefer the option to download citations in standard styles (e.g., APA, MLA, Chicago) instead?
- Was the download method simple and functional?
- Is there anything you would improve in the display of bibliographic data or the download options?

(Encourage the participant to think out loud throughout this discussion.)

After Completing the Task – Metrics:

Sub-question 1:

- What is your overall impression of this activity?

Sub-question 2:

- On a scale of 1–5 (1 – not at all satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied), how satisfied are you with this experience?
 - Why did you give that rating? Please explain.

Sub-question 3:

- Is there anything you particularly liked about this experience?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask sub-questions to probe further.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it clear or simple?

Sub-question 4:

- Is there anything you didn't like about this experience?
 - Please explain your answer. *(Ask sub-questions to probe further.)*
 - E.g., Why did you find it unclear or difficult?

Sub-question 5:

- Do you have any suggestions to improve the experience of completing this task?

Transition to the Next Activity:

- Do you have any additional comments before we move on to the next activity?

Now, we will move on to the next activity.

[Moderator's Note:] Remind the participant to think aloud during the next task.

Scenario 6

To conclude the testing, we want to evaluate how useful the GoTriple platform is when you search using a query in Croatian. Imagine you are continuing your research on the challenges that artificial intelligence has raised in the field of education, but this time, you want to perform the search in Croatian.

Task 6: Comparison of Search in Croatian Language and Interface

Instructions:

- Return to the homepage of the GoTriple platform.
 - Switch the interface to Croatian.
 - Take a few moments to familiarize yourself with the appearance and functionality of the Croatian interface.
 - Perform a query in Croatian similar to the one you asked earlier in English, aiming for relevant results in your area of interest.
 - *(Example: If your previous query was "artificial intelligence in education," now try a similar query in Croatian.)*
 - Stay on the search results page briefly and review the displayed results in detail.
 - Think aloud as you analyze the results and share your observations about the presentation of the results and the terminology used.
 - If you encounter any difficulties or have questions, feel free to pause and ask me.
-

After Completing the Task – Discussion About the Experience:

- How did searching in Croatian compare to searching in English?
- Were the search results in Croatian as relevant as the results in English?
- Did you notice differences in the number and type of results displayed between Croatian and English?

- Were the results shown to you mostly in Croatian, or were there results in other languages as well? Did you notice the languages in which the results are displayed?
- Were you aware that searching in Croatian could return works in multiple languages?
- How important is it to you to search in Croatian and retrieve works in all available languages?
- Did anything surprise you about the way results were displayed, or did you expect different information?
- What would you suggest improving in the display of search results or in the Croatian functionality of the platform?

(Encourage participants to think aloud as they respond to these questions.)

Wrap-up

Thank you for participating in the testing of the GoTriple platform. To conclude, we would like to hear your overall impressions and any suggestions you have to further improve the user experience.

Questions:

- How would you describe your overall experience using the GoTriple platform?
- What was the most challenging task for you, and why?
- Did anything particularly frustrate or surprise you while using the platform?
- What improvements would you suggest for the results display or platform functionalities? Is there any additional functionality you would like to see on the platform?

On a scale of 0 to 10, how likely are you to recommend the GoTriple platform to your colleagues or friends?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Follow-up:

- What motivated you most to choose this rating?

Closing:

Once again, thank you for the time and effort you put into this testing. Your feedback is extremely valuable and will help us further improve the GoTriple platform.

Consent form (in Croatian)

Izjava o suglasnosti za sudjelovanje u istraživanju

Poštovani/a,

Ovim putem Vas pozivamo na sudjelovanje u istraživanju čiji je cilj testiranje upotrebljivosti platforme za pretraživanje literature, koje provodi Laboratorij za interaktivne sustave i korisničko iskustvo (UX lab Zadar) Sveučilišta u Zadru, u sklopu projekta OPERAS-PLUS - On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure.

Vaše sudjelovanje u istraživanju je dobrovoljno i u svakom trenutku možete odustati od sudjelovanja.

Cilj ovog istraživanja je testirati upotrebljivosti platforme, kako bi se prikupili podaci na temelju kojih bi se njena funkcionalnost.

Tijekom istraživanja, od Vas će se tražiti da koristite platformu putem računala te da odgovarate na pitanja vezana za Vaše iskustvo korištenja. Istraživanje će provesti moderator te kolege iz UX lab-a koji će voditi bilješke. Vaše aktivnosti na ekranu će se snimati, kao i audio i video zapis. Pristup prikupljenim podacima imat će djelatnici UX Laba Zadar. Prikupljeni podaci koristit će se isključivo u svrhu istraživanja, a rezultati će biti anonimizirani u skladu s Općom uredbom o zaštiti podataka (GDPR).

Ako ste suglasni, molim vas da to potvrdite potpisivanjem obrasca.

Hvala i srdačan pozdrav,

Ime i prezime : _____

Potpis: _____

Datum: _____

Appendix C - URUT script in English with consent form

Thank You for Joining This Study!

The purpose of this session is to evaluate the **GoTriple platform**, a discovery service for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research. Your feedback will help us identify what works well and what can be improved. This will allow us to enhance the user experience for all future users of GoTriple.

What is this study about?

- This research is part of the **OPERAS-PLUS** project, which supports **open scholarly communication** in SSH.
- We are testing the **GoTriple** platform to understand how users navigate, search, and interact with its features.
- Your insights will help **improve usability** and ensure GoTriple meets the needs of SSH researchers.

Consent

 [Full Consent Form PDF](#) (for details on data usage, retention, and privacy)

✗ If you prefer not to participate in this usability study, simply close this webpage. Wishing you a wonderful day!

✓ If you agree to participate, please confirm your consent by clicking the “Start” button below to proceed to the usability tasks.

FULL CONSENT FORM

Thank you for joining this study.

The purpose of this session is **to evaluate the GoTriple platform**. Your feedback will help us identify what works well within the platform and what can be improved. If you encounter any difficulties while using the system, it's likely that other users might face the same challenges. This is why your feedback is so important—it will allow us to

address these issues and enhance the user experience for all future users of the GoTriple platform.

Participant Information Sheet and Research Consent Form

Project Title: OPERAS-PLUS – Supporting the Development of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure in Its Preparatory Phase

Researcher Name(s): Franjo Pehar, Mate Juric, Nikolina Peša Pavlović (University of Zadar, members of the OPERAS-PLUS WP6 team)

Contact e-mail: uxlab@unizd.hr

What is the research about?

We invite you to participate in the research activities conducted under the **OPERAS-PLUS project**, specifically Work Package 6, Task 6.3. OPERAS is a Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area (ERA). This project aims to strengthen OPERAS' governance, services, and impact, empowering it to become operational as an ERIC by 2028.

Your participation will contribute to user engagement efforts, particularly by **helping us understand user needs and workflows** related to the OPERAS services.

Do I have to take part?

This form is designed to help you decide if you would like to take part. Participation is entirely voluntary. If you decide to participate, **you are free to withdraw at any time** without providing a reason and without penalty.

Your expertise and participation will help us improve the OPERAS services and align them with user needs. The insights gathered will contribute to shaping the platform and services to better support the SSH research community.

What will I be required to do?

You will be asked to participate in an unmoderated usability testing session. During this session, you will be provided with tasks to complete independently using the OPERAS services or platform. **You will have the option to allow the session to be audio and screen-recorded** to capture your interactions and verbal feedback. **If you do not consent to recording, you may still proceed with the session, and your written feedback will be collected instead.** To take part in this study, You will need to install a Chrome app "Loop11 User Testing" from Chrome Web Store or a mobile app from Google Play or Apple App Store, after giving consent to participate.

Unmoderated usability testing sessions typically take between 15-30 minutes.

How will you handle my data?

Your data will be pseudonymized and stored securely. This means that **your personal data will be replaced by codes**. A separate key linking your personal information to the research data will be stored securely and separately. Only authorized researchers from the University of Zadar will have access to your data. Your data will be stored on a secure drive, and pseudonymization will occur at the earliest opportunity.

Your responses will remain confidential, and **individuals will not be identifiable** in any research dissemination (e.g., publications or presentations).

The recording of your session (if you consent to recording) will be used solely for analysis purposes and will not be shared outside the research team. Any analysis involving cloud-based software will comply with GDPR standards.

Retention of Research Data

Research data will be retained for up to 10 years post-publication, consistent with data retention policies. **Anonymized data** may be retained indefinitely for open science practices, enabling other researchers to verify findings. If the dataset is deemed of scientific interest, anonymized data may be deposited in an open-access repository, such as Zenodo, after publication.

Consent forms will be retained for as long as information about a data subject is held and for a minimum of 10 years post-publication.

Consent Statement

This consent form is designed to ensure ethical research practices. By indicating your consent, you agree to participate in this research under the following terms:

1. I understand the contents of the participant information sheet and consent form.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without penalty and without explanation.
3. I understand how my data will be handled and who will have access to it.
4. I understand that the session may be recorded (audio and/or screen) if I provide my consent, but I may also participate without recording.

Consent Confirmation

By completing this form, I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided and agree to participate in the research under the conditions outlined.

The study with the consent confirmation button is available here:

A. If you are willing **to share your screen** (ideally using Google Chrome), please use the following link to start the session:

[LINK 1](#)

B. If you encounter issues with screen sharing or prefer **not to share your screen**, please use this alternative link:

[LINK 2](#)

Would you be willing to share your microphone and speak in English?

- Yes, I will share my microphone and speak in English during the usability tasks.
- No, I won't share my microphone. I'll provide written feedback only.

[Conditional Logic - further instructions include Think Aloud protocol if audio sharing is selected.

Below is the script IF screen and audio sharing are selected]

Welcome and thank you for participating!

In this study, we'd like your feedback on the GoTriple platform.

- ◆ You will complete four tasks, followed by a few questions about your experience.
- ◆ First, a short introductory task will help you get familiar with the testing tool.

 Before you begin, you may be prompted to “Install the official (Loop11) App” to record your session. If you already have it installed, you will proceed directly to the next step.

In some cases, a **quick browser restart** might be needed after installation. You may also see a prompt to **allow recording permissions** (screen, microphone, or camera)—just follow the on-screen instructions. If you're using **macOS Catalina (10.15) or later**, you might need to enable **Screen Recording and Microphone access** in your system settings. If you're using **Edge**, you might need to **activate the extension Loop11**, in Edge Settings > Extensions.

 If you are **on a Desktop computer**, to **share** your screen please select sharing the **entire browser window**, not just a single tab.

98

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

📌 If you are **on a mobile device**, when sharing your screen make sure to **select the Loop11 app icon rather than the suggested screen** option. **Once the green Loop11 screen appears, tap the Back button** to return to the instructions screen.

🗣️ **As you complete the tasks, please talk us through your thinking and verbalise your thoughts.**

💡 This session typically takes around 25-30 minutes.

! **Prefer not to enable screen recording or microphone access?** You can still participate by providing **written feedback**. You will **still need to “Install the official App”**, but you can later decline recording permissions. The alternative version of the study is available via the **link shared in your email invitation**.

Click ➡ **Next** to begin!

How to use this testing tool and environment?

- ◆ First, read these instructions carefully before starting.
 - You will interact with the **GoTriple platform** while following task instructions.
 - The task menu will **disappear** when you start a task, but you can bring it back.
 - You can toggle between **↑ SHOW** and **HIDE ↓** to access or hide the instructions.
- ◆ Once you have read these instructions, follow these steps:
 1. **Click ▶ START TASK** to begin. This will **minimise the task menu**, and it will disappear from view.
 2. **To bring the task menu back, click the ↑ SHOW circle/button** in the bottom left corner of your screen.
 - **If the ↑ SHOW circle disappears, refresh the page (F5 on desktop or pull-to-refresh on mobile)** to restore it.
 3. **To toggle the task menu visibility:**
 - Click **↓ HIDE** to hide the menu and explore the GoTriple platform.
 - Click **↑ SHOW** to return to the instructions.
- ◆ Before starting the first task:
 1. Click **↓ HIDE** to interact with the page and set the GoTriple interface to **English** (if it's not already).
 2. Click **↑ SHOW** to reopen the task menu.

3. Clicking **ABANDON TASK** will **skip the current task** and move directly to the follow-up questions.
4. Click **TASK COMPLETED** to proceed to the first GoTriple-related task.

[Start URL: <https://www.gotriple.eu/>]

Have you used GoTriple before? If so, how frequently?

- This is my first time
 - Rarely
 - Monthly
 - Weekly
 - Daily
-

Task 1: Explore the GoTriple Homepage

Imagine you have just arrived at the **GoTriple homepage**.

◆ **Before clicking on anything, explore the homepage as you naturally would when visiting a new online platform for the first time.**

Take a couple of minutes to scroll and analyse, but please do not click yet.

- ◆ **As you explore, carefully analyse the page** and **think aloud** about:
 - **What does this platform seem to be used for?**
 - **What kinds of research materials, tools, or services appear to be available?**
 - **What stands out to you the most?**

 Click ▶"START TASK" when you're ready and "TASK COMPLETED" when you finish the task.

[Start URL: <https://www.gotriple.eu/>]

? Based on what you explored, what do you think this platform is used for?

- Was it immediately clear what GoTriple offers, or did you have to look for information?

? What stood out to you the most on the homepage?

- Did anything seem unclear, distracting, or confusing?
 - Does GoTriple seem to offer more than just a research database?
-

? **Based on your first impression, how clear or confusing was it to understand what GoTriple offers and how you can use the platform?**

- Select a number from 1 (very confusing) to 5 (very clear).
- If you'd like, you can also explain your choice by speaking aloud.

Rating scale:

- 1 = very confusing
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 = very clear
-

? **How clear or confusing were the labels and terminology on the homepage?**

- Select a number from 1 (very confusing) to 5 (very clear).
- If you'd like, you can also explain your choice by speaking aloud.

Rating scale:

1 1 = very confusing

-
- 2 2
 - 3 3
 - 4 4
 - 5 5 = very clear
-

? What, if anything, would you improve on the homepage to make it clearer or easier to use?

- write your response instead.
 - If you don't have any suggestions, you can skip this question by clicking "**Next**"
-

Task 2: Search for Publications

Imagine you are using **GoTriple** to find **publications** on a topic of interest to you.

- ♦ **Enter a search query** in the search bar that reflects your research topic or area of interest.
- ♦ **As you type and search, think aloud** about:
 - How are you **choosing your search terms**?
 - What do you **expect to see** in the results?
- ♦ **Review the search results and continue thinking aloud** as you reflect on:
 - **How relevant** are the results to your query?
 - **Do they match your expectations?** Why or why not?

** Important:**

- **Do not use filters, the knowledge graph, or other tools.**
 - **Perform a single search and review the results.**
-

-
- If you get no results, you may modify your search phrase.

💡 Click ▶ "START TASK" when you're ready and "TASK COMPLETED" when you finish the task.

[Start URL: <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

Success URLs:

contain: documents]

? How easy or difficult was it to use the search function?

- Select a number from **1 (very difficult)** to **5 (very easy)**, or choose "I can't estimate."
- 🧠 As you select your answer, **think aloud** about why you chose this rating.

Rating scale:

- 1 = very difficult
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 = very easy
 - I can't estimate
-

? How relevant were the search results to your topic?

- Select a number from **1 (not relevant at all)** to **5 (highly relevant)**, or choose "I can't estimate."
- 🧠 As you select your answer, **think aloud** about why you chose this rating.

Rating scale:

- 1 = completely irrelevant
 - 2
-

-
- 3
 - 4
 - 5= completely relevant
 - I can't estimate
-

? Based on your experience searching for publications, how important do you think the following system functionalities would be for improving the search experience in GoTriple?

- Select a number from the scale below, or choose "I can't estimate."
- As you select your ratings, **think aloud** about why these features would (or wouldn't) be helpful.

Highlight and correct misspelled words in the search bar (e.g., show suggestions if a term is mistyped).

Display similar search terms while typing (e.g., autocomplete suggestions to refine queries).

Provide contextual search help (e.g., in-page hints, tooltips, or a guided tour) to explain search features and improve discoverability (Help, Tutorials, FAQ).

Allow advanced searches with multiple search fields (e.g., search by title, abstract, keyword, author; discipline; projects).

Rating scale:

- 1 = Not important at all
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 = Extremely important
 - I can't estimate
-

? **Do you have any comments about your experience searching for publications?**

- write your response instead.
 - Mention anything that worked well or anything that was unclear or frustrating.
 - If nothing stands out, you can skip this question by clicking "Next."
-

Task 3: Refine and Sort Search Results

Now, let's **refine your search** to find the most **relevant** and **specific** publications for your needs.

 Remember to **think aloud** as you complete this task. **Describe your choices, expectations, and any difficulties you encounter.**

◆ **Start by running a new search**—repeat your previous query or modify it slightly if needed.

◆ **Next, apply filters to narrow your results:**

- **Discipline** – Select your academic field.
- **Preferred language** – Choose a language you typically read in.
- **Content type** – Show only articles.
- **Publication date** – Display only results from the last 5 years.

◆ **Once you've applied filters, sort the results by date** to bring the most recent publications to the top.

◆ **Finally, review your refined search results.**

- Do the filtering and sorting options help you find what you need? Were there any difficulties?

 Click ▶"START TASK" when you're ready and "TASK COMPLETED" when you finish the task.

[Start URL: <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

Success URLs:

- contains: typ_article
 - contains: in_language
 - contains: most_recent
 - contains: year
 - contains: topic
 - Success URL Rules: All]
-

? How easy or difficult was it to locate and apply the filters?

- Select a number from **1 (very difficult)** to **5 (very easy)**, or choose "I can't estimate."
- As you select your answer, **think aloud** about why you chose this rating.

Rating scale:

- 1 - Very difficult
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 - Very easy
 - I can't estimate
-

? How easy and clear was it to find and use the sorting options (e.g., sorting by publication date)?

- Select a number from the scale below, or choose "I can't estimate."
-

-
- As you select your answer, **think aloud** about why you chose this rating.

Rating scale:

- 1 - Very difficult
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 - Very easy
 - I can't estimate
-
-

Task 4: Explore a Publication in Detail

Now, let's **take a closer look at a publication** from your search results.

- ◆ **Start by running a new search**—repeat your previous query or modify it slightly if needed.
- ◆ **Select one publication from the search results and examine its details as you would when assessing its usefulness for your research.**

 As you explore, **think aloud. Describe your choices, expectations, and any difficulties you encounter.**

- ◆ **Review key publication details**, including:
 - **Bibliographic information** (e.g., author, title, publication date, source) to understand the publication's origin and credibility.
 - **Additional metadata** (e.g., abstract, keywords) to determine its relevance and research scope.

 Click ▶"START TASK" when you're ready and "TASK COMPLETED" when you finish the task.

[Start URL: <https://www.gotriple.eu>]

? How well did the publication details page present the information you needed?

 Please **think aloud** as you reflect. If you prefer, you can write your response instead.

- Were any important details missing?
 - Was anything unclear or difficult to find? (You may consider metadata, structure, or clarity.)
 - If nothing stands out, you can skip this question by clicking "Next."
-

? Please rate the importance of improving how publication details (metadata) are displayed and structured in GoTriple by incorporating the following functionalities:

 Feel free to **think aloud** if something stands out to you.)

Show full abstracts by default without requiring a 'Show more' click.

Ensure every bibliographic record includes complete metadata, structured for clarity and consistency.

Use color-coded labels to clearly indicate open access and restricted content, making it easier for users to identify full-text availability at a glance.

- 1 = Not important at all
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 = Extremely important
 - I can't estimate
-

Keep Track of a Relevant Publication

Imagine you have come across a publication that **resonates with your research**—one you may want to **include in your current work or keep for future reference**.

◆ **In the next step, you will see the full details of a publication. For the purpose of this task, assume it is relevant to you.**

◆ **Use the options available on the page, or any method you normally use, to save this publication for future reference or to immediately include it in your writing.**

💡 Remember to **think aloud** as you complete this task. Say what you would **normally do to save a useful publication and whether the options on this page work for you**. If anything is **unclear or missing**, mention it aloud.

💡 Click ▶ **"START TASK"** when you're ready and **"TASK COMPLETED"** when you finish the task.

[Start URL:

https://www.gotriple.eu/documents/50%7Cdoiboost_%3A%3A8c2036a0e5b27c783547c92e73379eba Document page for: Terras, M., Nyhan, J., & Vanhoutte, E. (Eds.). (2013). *Defining Digital Humanities: A Reader* (1st ed.). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315576251>]

? **How well did the available options on this page support the way you usually track and save publication references?**

- 💡 **Think aloud or write your response.**
 - **Did you find the formats you normally use for saving, citing, or exporting references?**
-

-
- **Were any important options missing compared to what you typically rely on?**
-
-

? Please rate the importance of improving citation and reference export options in GoTriple by incorporating the following functionalities:

(💡 Feel free to think aloud if something stands out to you.)

Copy preformatted citations in APA, MLA, Chicago, and other common styles directly from the platform—ready to paste into your document.

In addition to BibTeX and JSON, allow exporting references in RIS, Zotero RDF, and CSV for easy use in reference managers (e.g., Zotero, EndNote) or research data tools like spreadsheets.

- 1 = Not important at all
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 = Extremely important
 - I can't estimate
-
-

Share Your Overall Experience with GoTriple

Now that you've completed the tasks, we'd like to hear your overall thoughts on the GoTriple search platform.

♦ In this section, you will rate different aspects of your experience, including design, usability, and overall impressions.

◆ You will be presented with opposing terms (e.g., "Unattractive" vs. "Attractive") and asked to rate GoTriple on a scale from 1 to 7.

Example:

Unattractive 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Attractive

(A response of 6 means you find the system more attractive than unattractive.)

- ◆ There are no right or wrong answers—we're interested in your honest opinion based on your experience.
- ◆ If unsure, go with your best estimate.

Which of the following opposing terms better describes GoTriple?

[Rating Scale Matrix Question Type]

[Subjects:]

- Confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Clear
- Inefficient 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Efficient
- Complicated 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Easy
- Obstructive 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Supportive
- Boring 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Exciting
- Not interesting 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Interesting
- Conventional 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Inventive
- Usual 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Leading edge

[Rating options:]

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

? Please rate your experience with the GoTriple platform by indicating how strongly you agree or disagree with the following statements.

- ◆ There are no right or wrong answers—only your personal opinion matters.
-

 Example:

"I thought this platform was easy to use."

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 **Strongly Agree**

◆ **Select the response that best reflects your experience.**

- I think that I would like to use this platform frequently
- I found this platform unnecessarily complex
- I thought this platform was easy to use
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this platform
- I found the various functions in this platform were well integrated
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this platform
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this platform very quickly
- I found this platform very cumbersome / awkward to use
- I felt very confident using this platform
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this platform

Rating scale

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree or disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

[Note: reverse coding for items 2, 4, 6, 8, 10]

? How likely are you to recommend the GoTriple platform to your colleagues, peers, or friends?

◆ **Select the number that best reflects your opinion.**

- 0 = Not at all likely
 - 1
-

-
- 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - 10 = Extremely likely
-

Finally, a few demographic questions to better understand responses.

- ◆ Your answers are **anonymous** and will only be used for research purposes.

? What is your primary academic background?

- Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Other, please specify: ____
-

? What best describes your current role(s)?

- ◆ **(Select all that apply)**

- Student (BA/MA)
 - PhD Student
 - Academic Researcher
 - Teaching Faculty member
 - Librarian
 - Publisher
 - Project Manager
 - Industry Professional
 - Archivist
-

-
- Unemployed
 - Retired
 - Independent Researcher
 - Open Science Practitioner
 - Other, please specify: ____
-

? What is your primary language for academic work or research?

- English
 - Italian
 - French
 - German
 - Polish
 - Portuguese
 - Croatia
 - Slovenian
 - Spanish
 - Other, please specify: ____
-

? What other languages do you use for academic work or research?

- English
 - Italian
 - French
 - German
 - Polish
 - Portuguese
 - Croatia
 - Slovenian
 - Spanish
 - Other, please specify: ____
-

? Have you been involved in the development of the GoTriple platform or other OPERAS projects?

- No
- Yes, I worked on GoTriple development.
- Yes, I contributed to other OPERAS projects.
- Yes, in other projects. Please specify. ____

? Do you have any suggestions to improve the tasks, instructions, or questions in this study?

◆ **For example:** Were any tasks unclear? Did you encounter technical issues? How could we make this experience better?

💡 Feel free to **think aloud** or **write** your response—whichever you prefer.

💡 If you have no suggestions, feel free to click "**Next.**"

Appendix D - Extracts from HE, MUT, and URUT reports

This appendix contains selected extracts from the internal HE and MUT reports, which are confidential and for internal use only. These reports are not publicly available, and the information included here is only shared to provide internal insight into research questions, usability challenges, task effectiveness and evaluation method findings.

The extracts are anonymised and categorised by method to provide additional context beyond the structured findings in the main report. While valuable for internal reference, these findings are restricted to authorised project stakeholders and will not be shared externally.

WP6 - Heuristic evaluation report - 15-11-2024-2.docx

- **The heuristic evaluation identified a severe usability problem with the Go Triple platform's search functionality, specifically regarding the handling of special characters and diacritics, which leads to irrelevant search results.**

“Certain characters (special characters and diacritics) are not correctly recognized and processed by the search system. The search functionality does not correctly handle special characters like "ž," which leads to irrelevant search results. For example, I have used "afž" and the system provided irrelevant results related to "afz.”

- **The heuristic evaluation revealed a severe usability problem with the Go Triple platform's sign-up process, where users are confused by the requirement to have an OPERAS ID without any explanation of what it is.**

“The signup page says "Register an Operas account or simply connect to your own", but then on the same screen you are asked to enter your OPERAS ID. Also, no one explains what an OPERAS ID is - it's completely unclear.”

- **The heuristic evaluation found a severe usability problem in the Go Triple platform's login process, where the 'Are you an author' section does not offer enough options, leading to potential confusion about user status.**

“The "Are you an author" section does not offer enough options. Only one button is offered. "I am the author". If only a single option is offered, users may feel trapped as they are unable to state their true status.”

- **The heuristic evaluation identified a severe usability problem with the Go Triple platform's homepage/navigation, where the use of confusing terms like 'Report an issue' for membership inquiries misaligns with user expectations.**

“When users try to access the membership options, they are instructed to

"Report an issue" to inquire about membership, which is inconsistent with their expectations and causes confusion. The term "Report an issue" is unrelated to a membership enquiry."

- **Participants identified confusing terms and unclear instructions as significant usability challenges, particularly in the sign-up and navigation processes.**

"The signup page says 'Register an Operas account or simply connect to your own', but then on the same screen you are asked to enter your OPERAS ID. Also, no one explains what an OPERAS ID is - it's completely unclear."

"When users try to access the membership options, they are instructed to 'Report an issue' to inquire about membership, which is inconsistent with their expectations and causes confusion."

- **Participants highlighted the need for better user control and freedom, such as undo options and clearer navigation paths.**

"Integration problems with OPERAS SSO: I click on sign up with a new OPERAS account, if I find a problem and click back to the portal, it takes me to OPERAS login page, I lose GoTriple."

"When Logging out it's not really clear what it means. (logging out from GoTriple or Operas Id). There is no undo option."

- **Participants noted the lack of error feedback and guidance as a major issue, affecting task effectiveness and user experience.**

"When users enter one or two characters (e.g., acronyms like 'IT') in the search bar, they receive a generic error message that says, 'Please insert a valid search term before launching your search.' This does not clarify why the input is invalid, especially for valid acronyms or short terms."

"The system does not provide any feedback, so users do not know what happened or how to correct it. In addition, the home page lacks help resources to guide users on how to search effectively."

- **The evaluation method insights revealed that heuristic evaluation effectively identified severe usability problems, but participant comments provided additional context and depth to these findings.**

"The heuristic evaluation identified a total of 159 usability problems (severity 1-3) before the consensus."

"The evaluation was conducted by a group of five independent usability

experts who independently reviewed the platform and categorized the issues according to their severity.”

REPORT_Task 6.3_OPERAS-deliverable-WP6_task 6.3._Moderated usability testing.docx

- **Participants expected more complete bibliographic records, including publication title, pages, and DOI, and found the 'undefined' license label unhelpful.**
“If there is no licence, it is better not to put it, than put "undefined licence”.”
- **Participants found the 'Membership' and 'Data services' sections unclear, questioning their purpose and functionality.**
““Membership” - it's not clear what that means. I see discipline filters available. Data services - it's not clear.”
- **Participants noted the absence of a filter for their specific field, such as information sciences, and expressed dissatisfaction with the breadth of search results.**
“There is no filter for my field? No information sciences. I would expect that it is there.”

“I am not satisfied with the results, they are too wide”
- **Participants expressed a need for advanced search options and clearer search functionalities, including the ability to see the entire search query and use natural language.**

“It would be good to see the entire query that I put. The query is in English, and the keywords are in French, more information about the work should be included.”
- **Participants found the translation in the Croatian interface sometimes incorrect, which could affect credibility.**
“The translation is unusual, sometimes wrong, it may seem uncredible to some users when they see a bad translation.#
- **Participants highlighted the lack of a filter for the field of information science and the inability to see the full abstract on the results page, which are severe usability problems.**

“there is no filter for my field (information sciences)”

"it would be better if the entire abstract could be seen on the list of the results page; it is too short now"

- **Participants found the translation in the Croatian interface sometimes incorrect, which could affect credibility and usability.**

"the translation is unusual, sometimes wrong, it may seem unbelievable to some users when they see a bad translation"

- **Participants expressed confusion about the 'Recommended' function and the lack of clarity regarding 'Membership' and 'Data services', indicating usability challenges in understanding platform features.**

"Membership" - it's not clear what that means. I see discipline filters available. Data services - it's not clear. Search resources and users - are they users, so I am searching for people - am I searching for authors - this is not intuitive. I would expect a natural language search but there is no link to an advanced search."

- **Participants expressed dissatisfaction with incomplete bibliographic records, missing important elements such as publication title, pages, and DOI, which are severe usability problems.**

"bibliographic records are not complete: missing: publication title, pages, licence (f.e. it is undefined), DOI, affiliation, type of document, is this publication in some database (Web of Science, CC etc.), citation would also be good what is undefined - it is not clear"

- **Participants found the search results page cluttered with too many keywords and noted that the left part of the screen was too wide, impacting task effectiveness and usability.**

"too many keywords on the results page"

"the left part of the screen should be narrower (2 out of 6 participants)"

- **Participants noted the absence of advanced search options and the inability to search across different fields, which are significant usability challenges affecting task effectiveness.**

"no possibility to search different fields (e.g. abstract), e.g. via the advanced search (3 of 6)"

"no options for selecting the Boolean operator, you have to type it in"

Appendix E - Methodological guidelines for HE, MUT, and URUT

This appendix contains detailed methodological guidelines for conducting heuristic evaluation (HE), moderated usability testing (MUT), and unmoderated remote usability testing (URUT) in the context of scholarly communication and open science services.

How to conduct a HE for scholarly communication and open science services

This guide provides an overview of how to conduct a HE of scholarly communication and open science services. A detailed description, including evaluation criteria, expert responses and full methodological documentation, is available in the internal report:

 [WP6 - Heuristic evaluation report.docx](#) (access is restricted to members of the project team).

A HE is a structured expert review used to identify usability problems in a system. This method is particularly valuable for scholarly communication and open science services, where efficient access to research results, intuitive navigation and clear system feedback are essential for different user groups, including researchers, librarians and students.

Our evaluation of the GoTriple platform followed Jakob Nielsen's 10 usability heuristics and applied a severity rating system to prioritise issues. The step-by-step process for HE of scholarly communication services is outlined below.

Step 1: Define scope and objectives

Before carrying out the heuristic evaluation, it is essential to get familiar with the system (website or application) that is going to be evaluated. In an ideal scenario, the entire system needs to be evaluated using some of the proposed heuristics.

If the system is complex, it is important to identify a compact part of the system to be evaluated, such as the examples below:

1. Key areas for evaluation

Focus on critical user interactions such as

- Home page & navigation - Clarity of structure, terminology and ease of access.
- Search functionality - Efficiency, accuracy and relevance of search results.
- Login & Registration Process - Ease of account creation and authentication.
- Error messages & system feedback - Clarity, helpfulness and guidance for users.
- Or other aspects specific to the service being evaluated.

2. Evaluation team and evaluators

Heuristic evaluation should be prepared and conducted by trained UX specialists, as they have the expertise to systematically identify usability problems based on established heuristics.

However, for evaluations in scholarly communication and other specialised domains, it may be beneficial to include additional experts who can provide context-specific

insights. A balanced evaluation team might include

- UX specialists - To lead the evaluation process, prepare the methodology, select the heuristics, conduct the review and consolidate the findings.
- Domain experts (e.g., open science experts, researchers, or subject matter experts) - Provide insights into specific user workflows, disciplinary expectations, and content relevance.
- Software testing and quality assurance specialists - provide perspectives on system stability, functional usability and technical barriers.

All evaluators should follow a structured heuristic evaluation approach, where UX specialists define the evaluation framework and lead the process, while domain experts provide valuable contextual feedback to ensure that the platform meets the needs of its target users.

3. Evaluation criteria

What framework to use? There are several heuristics proposed by different authors. The most used is :

- Jakob Nielsen's 10 usability heuristics or other relevant UX principles or a custom framework tailored to the specific platform.

Other examples of heuristics that can be used for conducting HE are:

- Peter Morville's honeycomb
- Ben Schneiderman's

The ideal scenario is to propose and pretest heuristics for open science services and systems .

Step 2: Decide what scale of severity rating to use:

There are several scales to be used. One example is:

- 0 - No usability problem - No usability issues were identified in the area evaluated.
- 1 - minor usability problem - Minor impact on the user experience, unlikely to prevent a task from being completed. These issues are usually cosmetic or minor usability problems that can be easily resolved.
- 2 - Moderate usability problem - Noticeable problems that could affect the user experience but do not prevent the user from completing tasks. These problems require attention and could improve the user experience if fixed.
- 3 - Major usability problem - Critical issues that significantly disrupt the user experience or prevent users from completing important tasks. These issues should be prioritized for immediate resolution.

Step 3: Select and train evaluators

122

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A successful heuristic evaluation typically involves 3 to 5 experts, including

- Usability/UX specialists - Identify standard usability violations and interface inconsistencies.
- Open science and scholarly communication experts - Ensure alignment with research workflows and accessibility principles.
- Subject matter experts (researchers, librarians) - Provide domain-specific insights.

Evaluators need to be trained to:

- Apply heuristics systematically or use other relevant UX principles and frameworks as appropriate for the evaluation.
- Use a consistent severity rating scale.
- Avoid bias or personal preferences and focus on objective usability issues.

Step 4: Conduct individual evaluations

Each evaluator independently evaluates the platform and documents:

- Usability violations, noting which heuristic is affected.
- Where and how the problem occurs, with screenshots where appropriate.
- A severity rating (from minor irritation to critical task failure).

Step 5: Expert consensus & consolidation of findings

Following the individual assessments, the findings are aggregated in a consensus meeting where experts will

- Discuss discrepancies in findings.
- Agree on the most critical usability issues.
- Prioritise issues based on their impact on task success and user frustration.

Step 6: Report key findings & recommendations

Findings are structured into:

- Summary of key usability problems, categorised by heuristic violation.
- Serious usability problems that require immediate attention.
- Positive usability aspects that should be maintained or improved.
- Actionable recommendations for resolving major issues.

Step 7: Triangulate and validate findings with user testing

Since heuristic evaluation does not involve real end users, the final step is to triangulate findings through user testing and behavioural data analysis to ensure accuracy and effectively prioritise issues, for example:

- MUT - Observing real user problems.
- URUT- Collecting larger amounts of usability data.
- Analytics & heatmaps - Confirm behavioural patterns.

 While HE can be used as a **stand-alone method**, its effectiveness depends on the goal and purpose of the evaluation. Like any other method, it provides valuable insights

on its own, but the best results come from systematically combining different methods that reveal complementary aspects of usability issues. HE is particularly useful for early stage evaluations and identifying obvious usability flaws, while user testing and behavioural data help to validate findings and capture more nuanced user interactions that HE alone might miss.

For a detailed inventory of methods and tools for UCD practice and their systematic application, see **UCQ FRAME, Section B** (Pehar & Pavlović, 2023).

Why HE is essential for open science services

- Improve platform accessibility and usability for researchers.
- Identifies problems before user testing, saving time and resources.
- Ensures alignment with open science principles, reducing barriers to knowledge.

Through systematic heuristic evaluation, research infrastructures and their services can improve accessibility, usability and efficiency, contributing to a FAIRer (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) open science ecosystem.

How to conduct a MUT for scholarly communication and open science services

This guide provides an overview of how to conduct MUT for scholarly communication and open science services. A detailed description, including test protocols, participant responses and full methodological documentation, is available in the internal report:

 REPORT_Task 6.3_OPERAS-deliverable-WP6_task 6.3_Moderated usability testing.docx (access restricted to project team members).

MUT is a user-centred evaluation method in which **real users perform tasks under the guidance of a moderator**. It is particularly valuable for scholarly communication services where efficient navigation, intuitive search functionality and clear system feedback are essential for users.

Our evaluation of the GoTriple platform followed a structured MUT methodology, using usability metrics and severity ratings to identify key areas for improvement. Below is a step-by-step guide to conducting moderated usability testing in scholarly communication services.

Step 1: Define scope and objectives

Before conducting MUT, it is essential to create a **usability testing plan**. This plan should include key evaluation areas, test goals, expected outcomes, and logistical details such as test environment and tools used (face-to-face or remote). Before conducting MUT, it is essential to determine:

Key areas for evaluation

The key areas for evaluation will depend on the topic, service or platform being researched. Examples of critical user interactions to focus on include

- Home Page & Navigation - Clarity of structure, terminology and ease of access.
- Search functionality - Efficiency, accuracy and relevance of search results.
- Login & Registration Process - Ease of account creation and authentication.
- Error messages & system feedback - Clarity, helpfulness and guidance for users.
- Other relevant interactions and related usability factors may be considered depending on the service or platform being tested.

Selection of participants and test roles

MUT relies on real users performing tasks under controlled conditions to identify usability problems. The testing process includes:

Selection of participants

- 5-6 participants from relevant user groups (e.g. researchers, librarians, students).
- Participants should have different levels of experience with the platform to reflect real-world usage.
- If we have different user groups, it is important to have 5-6 participants per each user group.

Testing roles

- Moderator - Conducts the session, follows the usability script, observes participants' actions and asks clarifying questions, scores task completion metrics and assigns problems, based on the user's inputs.
- Observer ("note taker") - Records participant behaviour, and takes notes, helps with assigning scores in task completion metrics, and task usability problems, notes-taking task-level satisfaction metrics.

Evaluation Criteria

What framework to use?

- Principles of task-based usability testing - Observing users performing specific tasks.
- Usability metrics - Task completion metric and user satisfaction scores.
- Severity rating scale - Categorising usability problems (see step 5).

Step 2: Select and prepare moderators

A successful moderated usability test requires trained moderators who can guide participants through tasks and facilitate discussions without influencing their answers.

Training of moderators

Moderators need to be trained to

- Facilitate sessions without leading participants to specific conclusions.
- Use a consistent usability script for structured testing.
- Apply the task success rating system and severity scale consistently.

Step 3: Conduct test sessions

Each usability testing session follows a structured process:

Pilot test

- Conduct a small pilot test to refine the usability test plan and script.
- Identify potential issues in the test setup before full deployment.

Main testing sessions

Each participant independently evaluates the platform and documents:

- Usability violations, noting which task is affected.
- Where and how the problem occurs, with screenshots where appropriate.
- A severity rating (from minor usability problems to severe usability problems and critical task failures). Each participant independently evaluates the platform and documents.

Step 4: Consolidating findings & reporting

After the test sessions, the results are analysed and structured into a formal report. This includes

- Synthesising usability problems from participant feedback.
- Documenting task completion metrics and severity of usability ratings.

- Analyzing satisfaction metrics (assigned by participants) - task level satisfaction metric and overall satisfaction.
- Organising findings into a pre-defined reporting template for consistency.
- Highlighting key usability problems and positive aspects to provide actionable recommendations. After individual assessments, the findings are consolidated into a structured report.

Step 5: Report key findings and recommendations

The findings are structured into

- Summary of key usability problems, categorised by task.
- Severe usability problems that require immediate attention.
- Positive aspects of usability that should be maintained or improved.
- Collected metrics.
- Actionable recommendations for solving major problems.

Step 6: Ethical considerations and data handling

As MUT involves real users, it is crucial to address ethical and privacy concerns:

- Informed Consent - Participants must be fully aware of the purpose of the study, the procedures, and how the data will be used.
- Data anonymisation - All responses collected should be anonymised to protect the privacy of participants.
- GDPR compliance - Ensure that all data collection and storage complies with data protection regulations.
- Participant wellbeing - Minimise cognitive load and stress, and allow participants to withdraw at any time.

Step 7: Triangulate and validate findings

As MUT captures real user behaviour, findings should be triangulated with

- HE - Cross-checking the findings of expert reviews.
- URUT - Collecting large amounts of usability data.
- Analytics & heatmaps - Confirming behavioural patterns.
- Other complementary methods from UCQ-FRAME Section B, such as long-term monitoring, user surveys and contextual queries, which provide further validation and deeper insights into the user experience.

📌 While MUT can be used as a **stand-alone method**, its effectiveness depends on the goal and purpose of the evaluation. Like any other method, it provides valuable insights on its own, but the best results come from systematically combining different methods that reveal complementary aspects of usability issues. MUT is particularly useful for validating findings from HE and capturing real user behaviour that experts may miss.

Why MUT is essential for open science services

- Improves accessibility and usability of the platform for researchers and other relevant user groups. While this study did not specifically include accessibility

testing, future research could extend this by including users with different accessibility needs, including users with visual impairments, to better assess and address potential barriers.

- Identifies usability problems in real user interactions.
- Supports iterative UX design and platform optimisation.
- Ensures alignment with Open Science and FAIR principles, reducing barriers to knowledge.

By systematically conducting MUT, research infrastructures and their services can refine their platforms to be more user-friendly, efficient and impactful in scholarly communication.

For a detailed inventory of methods and tools for UCD practice and their systematic application, see [UCQ FRAME](#), Section B (Pehar & Pavlović, 2023).

For a more detailed breakdown of the methodology, including full evaluation criteria, test scenarios and analysis of participants' responses, please refer to the internal report [REPORT_Task 6.3_OPERAS-deliverable-WP6_task 6.3._Moderated usability testing.docx](#) (restricted access).

How to conduct URUT for scholarly communication and open science services

This guide provides an overview of how to conduct a URUT for scholarly communication and open science services. A detailed description, including test protocols, participant responses and full methodological documentation, is available in the internal report:

 REPORT_Task 6.3_OPERAS-deliverable-WP6_task 6.3_Unmoderated usability testing.docx (access restricted to project team members).

URUT was conducted as the final phase of the GoTriple usability evaluation to validate the findings of HE and MUT. Unlike MUT, where facilitators guide participants, URUT requires users to complete tasks independently, reflecting natural user behaviour and decision-making processes in real-world conditions. This method allows for a more comprehensive, data-driven assessment of user interactions by collecting both quantitative usability metrics and qualitative user feedback.

URUT was designed to assess ease of navigation, task success rates and user satisfaction in an unmoderated environment. The study collected:

- Task success rates, clickstream data and response times.
- Post-test surveys (UEQ-S, SUS, NPS) to measure perceived usability, user experience and loyalty.
- Open-ended qualitative feedback to understand user frustrations, expectations and workflow efficiency.

Step 1: Define the research objective and research questions (RQ)

Before starting URUT, clearly define:

- Research objectives - What aspects of usability should be validated?
- Key research questions (RQ) - Which usability challenges should be quantified?
- Target audience - Which user groups should be involved?

Step 2: Select an online testing tool

Choose an online usability testing platform based on

- Support for both desktop and mobile interfaces.
- Ability to track task completion rates, clickstreams and screen recordings.
- Integration with post-test surveys (e.g. Loop11, Lookback, Optimal Workshop).

Step 3: Create a usability test plan

Structure the test around key usability tasks and user journeys:

- Define tasks aligned with RQs.
- Write clear, unambiguous instructions.
- Include informed consent and ethical guidelines.

Step 4: Select participants and define sample size

- Recruit at least 30+ participants for statistical robustness.
- Ensure diversity of user expertise and research background.
- Balance between first time and experienced users.

Step 5: Configure the online tool and provide clear instructions

- Set up structured task sequences.
- Enable screen and audio sharing for contextual insight.
- Ensure informed consent is obtained before testing begins.
- Test platform usability before launching URUT.

Step 6: Conduct pilot testing

- Conduct a small-scale test to identify inconsistencies in task flow and survey design.
- Adjust task difficulty based on feedback from pilot participants.
- Ensure session length is not excessive (optimal: 30-40 minutes).

Step 7: Conduct main test phase and collect data

- Each participant completes pre-defined tasks while the tool records.
- Task performance metrics (success/failure, completion time).
- Navigation paths and clickstream analysis.
- Post-task feedback (survey scores + open-ended comments).

Example of usability tasks evaluated in URUT

Task #	Scenario	Objective
Task 1	Explore the home page	Evaluate the clarity of the navigation, user orientation and first impression.
Task 2	Search for publications	Evaluate discoverability, efficiency and relevance of search results.
Task 3	Apply filters to refine search results	Test the usability, visibility and efficiency of search refinement options.
Task 4	Explore a publication's metadata and citation options	Evaluate the clarity and accessibility of bibliographic details and citation features.

Step 8: Analyse results and combine quantitative and qualitative data

- Analyse usability metrics using the online tool.
- Combine quantitative (task success, response times) and qualitative (user feedback) findings.
- Assess self-reported usability challenges through open-ended responses.
- Compare findings with MUT and HE for triangulated validation.

Step 9: Write the usability report

- Summarise key usability issues and severity ratings.
- Include statistical validation of findings (task success rates, time on task, etc.).
- Report user suggestions and qualitative feedback for redesign recommendations.

Key usability metrics used in URUT

Task-based performance metrics

- Task Success Rate - Percentage of participants who successfully complete tasks.
- Time on Task - Time taken to complete each task (efficiency measure).
- Error Rate - Number of incorrect actions per task.
- Navigation Complexity - Number of pages visited per task.

User reported metrics

- Ease of use ratings (1-5 Likert scale).
- Usability issues identified by users (open-ended responses).
- Suggestions for platform improvements.

Severity rating & issue prioritisation

Severity Level	Severity Definition
1 - Cosmetic	This problem has little or no impact on usability. It does not need to be fixed unless there is time, as it does not affect task completion.
2 - Minor usability problem	<p>Low priority problem, it needs to be removed, the user can still complete the task successfully, but with difficulties</p> <p>This is a low priority issue. It should be addressed, but will not prevent users from completing the task. However, users may experience some difficulties when interacting with the system.</p>
3 - Severe usability problem	This is a major issue that is preventing users from completing the task. This is a high priority issue and should be addressed as soon as possible.

Step 10: Validate findings through triangulation

URUT results should be validated using complementary methods to ensure a robust understanding of usability issues. Additional validation methods include

- HE - Cross-checking the findings of the expert review.
- MUT - Comparison of real-time observations.
- Analytics & Heatmaps - Confirm navigation patterns and behavioural trends.
- Long Term Monitoring & Surveys (UCQ-FRAME Section B) - Capture evolving

usability trends.

- User surveys and contextual queries - Providing further validation and deeper insights into the user experience beyond task completion rates.
- Comparative benchmarking - Benchmarking GoTriple against similar platforms to identify unique usability challenges and areas for improvement,
- or other methods listed in UCQ-FRAME, Section B.

📌 While URUT is highly effective for scalable usability testing, it is not ideal for deep qualitative insights into user behaviour and motivations. For qualitative data, interviews or MUT are preferable.

Why URUT is essential for open science services

- Confirms usability issues with a larger sample size.
- Provides statistically validated usability metrics.
- Captures real user interactions without external influence.
- Ensures compliance of services with Open Science and FAIR principles.

By systematically conducting URUT, research infrastructures can refine platforms to make them more user-friendly, accessible and efficient for scholarly communication.

